

D4.1 Report on Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions

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to 30/11/2025*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research and Innovation
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
YC	Youth Citizens
YAB	Youth Advisory Board
QH Cultural Hub	Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub

Abbreviation	Description
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE CH	EPIC-WE Cultural Hub
EPIC-WE CGJ	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
AUAS	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
DM	Dropstoff Media
NISV	Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
UL	Lusófona University
BS	Battleship
CMO	Obidós Municipal Council
AU	Aarhus University
AAKS	Filmby Aarhus
ARoS	ARoS Aarhus Kunstmuseum

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START

Executive Summary

01

1. Executive Summary

This report presents the outcomes of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the EPIC-WE project: *Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments*. The project explores how cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth can collaborate through Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) to reimagine cultural heritage and foster empowered participation. Building on the theoretical and methodological foundations developed in WP2 and WP3, WP4 applied an iterative Design-Based Research (DBR) approach to deliver and evaluate twelve interventions in the form of CGJs across three European Cultural Hubs: Aarhus (Denmark), Hilversum (Netherlands), and Óbidos (Portugal). These interventions tested how cross-sector collaboration can empower young people to become cultural game-makers, co-creating games that engage with heritage, identity, and values.

Through twelve CGJs, WP4 iteratively tested and evaluated how game-making can also function as culture-making. Participants collectively explored European values, heritage, and social issues, creating games that both reflected and reimagined their cultural heritage and environments. The iterative DBR process yielded insights into recruitment, facilitation, and documentation. Early challenges included difficulties recruiting diverse participants, balancing structure and freedom in the facilitation of the CGJs, and the burden of research protocols on participants. Adjustments in later CGJs through targeted recruitment, clearer onboarding, and flexible facilitation significantly improved engagement, inclusivity, and participant ownership.

A key innovation during WP4 was the role of Youth Advisory Boards (YABs). Formed after the first round of local CGJs, the YAB of each cultural hub supported CGJ planning, facilitation, and reflection. Their partnership elevated the role of youth from participants to co-creators but also highlighted tensions around fair remuneration, continuity, and decision transparency.

The findings underscore the transformative potential of CGJs as both method and medium for cultural empowerment and engagement. They enable CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth to “meet in the middle,” co-producing new forms of cultural participation and innovation that are locally grounded within the individual cultural hub site yet globally connected across the three Cultural Hubs in the project. Further, beyond the CGJs themselves, WP4 shifted from leading meetings to connecting and facilitating co-creation within the three international cultural hubs that could co-create and learn from one another as well also feeding into the refinement of the core research produced in WP2 and the core design innovations and methodologies developed for the CGJs in WP3 in the form of the Cultural Hub model, the Cultural Game Jam format, and the Cultural Game Jam Kit.

In conclusion, WP4 demonstrates that game-making is a viable and inspiring mode of cultural research, education, and innovation. By bridging creative practice and cultural heritage, the EPIC-WE CGJs have established a replicable model for empowering youth citizens to engage actively with cultural heritage and their cultural worlds, transforming them through play, imagination, and collaboration.

Introduction

02

2. Introduction

2.1 Overview of the Project Context (WP4) and Its Aims

This report outlines the implementation and outcomes of Work Package 4 (WP4) *EPIC-WE Local and Glocal Interventions* within the EPIC-WE: *Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments* project. WP4 examined how cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and young people can collaborate through Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) to reimagine culture and foster empowered participation. As the experimental and evaluative component of EPIC-WE, WP4 served as the setting where the theoretical grounding of the project in WP2 *State-of-the-art and Good Practices* and the Cultural Hub model and Cultural Game Jam format innovated and developed in WP3 *Ecosystems, Interventions and Methods* were tested in practice. By applying an iterative Design-Based Research (DBR) approach, WP4 explored how these innovations can support cultural institutions and creative industries in engaging young people with cultural heritage, values, and societal challenges.

WP4 was structured around four interconnected tasks designed to ensure iterative collaboration and shared learning across the project. Task 4.1 *Interventions Task Force* brought together representatives from each cultural hub to coordinate planning, exchange insights, and align implementation. Task 4.2 *Local and Glocal Site Interventions* focused on the delivery of twelve CGJ interventions across three European Cultural Hubs following the designs of WP3. Task 4.3 *Data Collection, Analysis and Evaluation* oversaw qualitative and quantitative research methods to assess how CGJs supported youth engagement, empowerment, creativity, and cross-sectoral collaboration. Finally, Task 4.4 *Local and Glocal Games Collections and Games Showcase* ensured that the games and resources produced during the CGJ interventions were documented, collected, curated, and shared through the EPIC-WE Resource Website (developed by WP5) as open-access materials for future use. Together, these tasks operationalised the DBR process, creating a continuous cycle of design, implementation, delivery, analysis, refinement, publication (between WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5).

The work undertaken in WP4 contributes directly to addressing the three central research questions (RQs) of the EPIC-WE project:

- **RQ1:** How can games be understood as significant culture and cultural worlds in their own right while also shaping identities, society and our cultural world in beneficial/harmful ways?
- **RQ2:** How can CHIs together with CIs facilitate cultural game jams to enable youth's widened and empowered participation in culture and cultural heritage through culture- and value-sensitive game-making?
- **RQ3:** How might young people come to see themselves as cultural game-makers and value-creators through game jamming with European cultures and values?

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What is the potential value of cultural game jams and helix systems for CHI, CI, youth, and European society?

RQ1 examines how games can be understood as cultural worlds that shape identities, societies, and cultures. RQ2 explores how CHIs, CIs, and HEIs can facilitate CGJs as culture- and value-sensitive interventions that empower youth participation in cultural heritage. RQ3 investigates how young people come to see themselves as cultural game-makers and value-creators, and what role CGJs in quadruple helix ecosystems can play in strengthening culture, creativity, and citizenship across Europe. WP4 provided the applied testing ground for these questions, producing both practical interventions and empirical evidence of their potential.

As the evaluation phase of the EPIC-WE DBR framework, WP4 aimed to execute, test, and assess the research outputs of WP2 and design outputs of WP3 through twelve CGJ interventions across the three cultural hubs. These interventions were implemented in two iterative rounds: an initial phase of six locally oriented CGJs that explored context-specific challenges and a second “glocal” phase that enabled exchange and adaptation of games between cultural hubs. Insights from each round were analysed, synthesised, and reintegrated into subsequent iterations, supporting alignment and cross-learning across the project’s work packages.

2.2 DBR Round 1: Six Locally-Oriented Cultural Game Jams

The first round of Design-Based Research (abbreviated as DBR; methodologically drawing on McKenney & Reeves, 2019) in 2024 focused on locally oriented CGJs in three cultural hubs, based in Aarhus, Denmark, Óbidos, Portugal, and Hilversum, Netherlands. Each cultural hub organised according to the **quadruple helix model**, with partners from research, cultural heritage, and creative industries working with youth, as found in Table 1.

	Aarhus Cultural Hub	Óbidos Cultural Hub	Hilversum Cultural Hub
Cultural Heritage	ARoS	City of Óbidos	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (Cultural Hub Lead)
Creative Industries	Filmby Aarhus	Battlesheep	Dropstuff Media
Higher Education	Aarhus University (Cultural Hub Lead)	Lusófona University (Cultural Hub Lead)	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
Youth Citizens	Youth Advisory Board and Youth Participants	Youth Advisory Board and Youth Participants	Youth Advisory Board and Youth Participants

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Table 1: Break-down of cultural hubs and partners

This quadruple helix model is based on [Protocol 1](#): *Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs* (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024a) from Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) *Protocols for carrying out cultural game jams in local sites*. D3.1 consisted of four individual sub-reports:

- [D3.1 Protocol 1](#): Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol)
- [D3.1 Protocol 2](#): Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Initial protocol)
- [D3.1 Protocol 3](#): EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol)
- [D3.1 Protocol 4](#): EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol)

After a pilot intervention by Aarhus in spring 2024, each cultural hub hosted two local CGJs. These piloted the **Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit)** from the [D3.1 Protocol 2](#): *Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools* (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024b), which introduced the four-phase **E-P-I-C model** (Experience, Play, Imagine, Create), the **World and Empowerment dimensions** or the W-E in EPIC-WE, the **core categories** of culture, values, citizenship, and games, and the **transition tools** (Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, Game Expo: Log and Pitch). To implement and evaluate the CGJ Kit, an initial set **practical protocols** [D3.1 Protocol 4](#) (Koppelman & Lennaerts, 2024) and **research protocols** [D3.1 Protocol 3](#) (Somers Miles et al., 2024) were also followed.

2.2.3 Importance of Game-making in Cultural Heritage with Youth

In the first CGJs hosted by each cultural hub, the CHI, HEI, and CI partners organised the events with youth primarily as participants. However, it became clear that to realise the ambitious ethos of the quadruple helix (QH) cultural hub model, youth citizens (YC) needed to be more than participants of the CGJ. Within QH ecosystems, the civic dimension is often treated as an audience or end-user of institutional initiatives rather than as an active agent in shaping them. To address this imbalance, the EPIC-WE project sought to reposition youth as co-creators within each cultural hub and recognise that meaningful empowerment would require shared ownership of implementation, reflection, and decision-making processes.

In response, each cultural hub established a Youth Advisory Board (YAB) before or shortly after their second CGJ, inviting four to six young people to act as advisors and co-researchers. This structure was first developed through focus groups with previous participants and young researchers, then refined and approved by the EPIC-WE Executive Board in summer 2024.

The incorporation of YABs embedded youth perspectives more deeply in the planning, facilitation, and evaluation of the Cultural Hubs and their CGJs. The YAB model was

intentionally iterative, with regular feedback loops that allowed YCs to help redefine their responsibilities and identify where their contributions could have the most value, both within the design of the CGJs and in the broader work of the cultural hubs. This approach aimed to reinforce the principle that YCs should be empowered partners in cultural research and innovation rather than only the beneficiaries of it. By sharing responsibility with the other QH Cultural Hub partners, youth participants shaped themes, activities, and facilitation strategies, turning CGJs into both methods for institutional learning and spaces for youth to experience agency.

2.3 DBR Round 2: Cultural Exchange Across the Three European Sites

The second round of DBR in 2025 introduced a refined methodology for cultural exchange, formalised in [D3.2 Protocol 2](#) (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025). Central to this stage was a **transnational and glocal approach**, which balanced attention to local contexts with opportunities for international cross-hub collaboration. During the six CGJs in the second DBR round, the three cultural hubs shared the Cultural Game Jam Kit developed in WP3, common themes, digital environments, and youth collaborations that linked their individual experiments into a shared learning ecosystem.

This refined implementation extended the CGJ Kit with adaptable formats for structuring a CGJ and delineated the difference between running a CGJ with games *through* culture and games *for* culture. **Games through culture** treat tangible cultural heritage as primary material for game-making. They integrate tangible heritage such as artworks, archival footage, architecture, or intangible oral histories as creative resources, transforming them into playable cultural worlds that reinterpret and reimagine cultural themes and meaning. These games are often heritage- and site-specific, drawing inspiration from cultural heritage collections or sites and re-presenting them through game mechanics, aesthetics, narratives, and interactive gameworlds. In contrast, **games for culture** use game-making as a creative, critical, or dialogic practice to explore intangible cultural heritage values, norms, themes, and civic imaginaries. They are explicitly value-driven, addressing topics such as inclusion, democracy, and identity through gameplay, narrative, and ethical design. Success is measured not by “fun gameplay” or “juicy aesthetics,” but by the game’s ability to generate cultural reflection, discussion, engagement, participation, empathy, and debate among players.

During DBR Round 2, the cultural hubs experimented with three initiatives for bringing a glocal dimension to their CGJs:

1. **Shared Themes:** *That’s Not Fair!* (three CGJs with Games for Culture) and *Heritage Remixed* (three CGJs with Games through Culture)
2. **Cross-CGJ communication:** Dedicated Discord environments and video greetings exchanged between cultural hubs

3. **Youth Advisory Boards (YABs):** Local YABs collaborating across cultural hubs, with representatives joining the EPIC-WE project-level Advisory Board

At the end of DBR Round 2, WP4 has met and even exceeded its proposed key performance indicators. The project delivered 12 cultural game jams (target: ≥ 12), engaged 424 young participants (target: ≥ 360), and supported the creation of 108 games (target: ≥ 84). These results confirm the scalability and impact of CGJs as a participatory format for empowered culture-making.

This report presents an overview of the twelve CGJs hosted across Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum, together with reflections on the implementation of the Cultural Game Jam format and Cultural Game Jam Kit developed in WP3. It details how the CGJs were planned and delivered, how youth and partners collaborated, and what lessons were drawn from these CGJ interventions. By embedding CGJs within quadruple helix ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs, EPIC-WE has developed a transferable framework where CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth co-create cultural worlds and environments. In doing so, the project demonstrates how *games through and for culture* can serve as powerful methods for reimagining cultural heritage, values, identity, citizenship, and belonging, positioning youth not only as participants but as empowered participants in and co-creators of Europe's cultural futures.

Methodology

03

3. Methodology

3.1 Overview of Practical Protocols

The practical implementation of CGJs was anchored in the **Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit)**, first developed and introduced in the [D3.1 Protocol 2](#) (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024) and further refined in [D3.2 Protocol 2](#) (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025). The CGJ Kit provided a structured methodology that could be applied consistently across cultural hubs while remaining adaptable to local and glocal needs. At its core was the **E-P-I-C process model**, which divides each CGJ into four stages: *Experience* (exploring cultural heritage collections, sites, and issues), *Play* (experimenting with connecting games and cultural heritage), *Imagine* (conceptualising and designing games with culture or games for culture), and *Create* (prototyping and presenting the games through/for culture at a cultural games EXPO in the cultural heritage institution).

These phases were supported by a set of **transition tools** to signify the shift from one phase to the next of the CGJ:

- **Ideation Wheel** (Experience): Helps participants experience and generate multiple ideas by exploring culture, values, citizenship, and game topics.
- **Expert Council** (Play): Provides youth with feedback from experts and professionals in games and culture targeting these intersections.
- **Playtest** (Imagine): Enables iterative refinement of the team's game through/for culture concept by constructing mock-ups or prototypes that enable participants to test and adjust their games based on playtesting.
- **Log & Pitch** (Create): Prepares teams to showcase their game through/for culture to audiences at the final EXPO and publish it at the open and online [EPIC-WE Resource Site](#).

The transition tools acted as bridges between the E-P-I-C phases, helping participants reflect, make decisions, and carry ideas forward. Together, the phases and tools provided a scaffolded yet flexible pathway for youth to move from inspiration to playable games through/for culture prototypes.

The CGJ Kit also emphasised four **core categories**: Culture, Games, Values, and Citizenship. These categories positioned CGJs as opportunities for heritage- and value-sensitive cultural game-making and civic reflection. Complementing this, the **World and Empowerment (W-E) dimensions** highlighted the dual focus on engaging with cultural worlds and strengthening youth agency. The World Dimension focuses on experience of and interaction with cultural gameworlds, storytelling, and values. Meanwhile, the Empowerment dimension encourages YC to engage with culture and cultural heritage

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through empowered participation, enabling them to become co-creators of games and culture, fostering cultural creativity, agency, and engagement.

The refinements introduced in [D3.2 Protocol 2](#); *Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools* built on the experiences of the first six CGJs. In this updated edition, seven fundamental principles for building a successful CGJ were defined (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025, pp. 37–39):

- **CGJ Principle 1:** Three ways to run Cultural Game Jams
- **CGJ Principle 2:** Aimed at cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment
- **CGJ Principle 3:** Foster cultural curiosity and creativity
- **CGJ Principle 4:** Cultivate an “epic we” through Cultural Game Jams
- **CGJ Principle 5:** Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making
- **CGJ Principle 6:** Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation
- **CGJ Principle 7:** Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

D3.2 Protocol 2 also introduced the updated Cultural Game Jam Kit and its three approaches for formatting a **CGJ: Focused, Flexible, and Freeform** (Nørgård and Holflod, 2025, p. 41). These formats enabled cultural hubs to tailor CGJs to their contexts while maintaining coherence across the project. In line with the Design-Based Research methodology, these refinements reflected a authentic and context-sensitive focus, ensuring that adaptations emerged from real-world practice rather than prescriptive models. This adaptability proved essential in DBR Round 2, where glocal collaboration required both alignment and openness to diversity.

Accompanying the CGJ Kit were **initial practical protocols devised in [D3.1 Protocol 4](#)** *EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites* (Koppelman & Lennaerts, 2024), which describes, how the Quadruple Helix Cultural Partners can work together in Cultural Hubs to facilitate CGJs. This report included requirements, reflections, and recommendations on:

- **Roles and responsibilities** in CHs before, during, and after running CGJs
- **Material and production** considerations when CHs are running CGJs
- **Networks** within the CHs are used to run CGJs
- **Recruitment** of participants for CGJs
- **Sustainable Development Goals** and their relation to CGJs

These reflections enable organisers of CGJs to position game-making as a form of culture-making and leads to the creation of games through and for culture. These practical protocols were also later refined in D3.2 Protocol 4 (Somers Miles et al., 2025b).

3.2 Overview of Research Protocols

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Running alongside these practical tools was the [D3.1 Research Protocol 3 EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites](#) (Somers Miles et al., 2024), and later the D3.2 Research Protocol 3 (Somers Miles et al., 2025a) that ensured systematic data collection and analysis. The protocol structured research activities before, during, and after each CGJ. Further, for each CGJ a dedicated table was produced to map these research activities, specifying their timing, purpose, participants, and methodological instruments used.

Before each CGJ, youth participants completed surveys capturing demographics, expectations, and prior experience, while cultural hub partners translated the project proposal goals into relevant KPIs regarding participant numbers, age/type of participants, number of games, style of CGJ, etc. These baseline instruments allowed the project to track change over time.

During the CGJs, multiple methods were used to capture lived experiences and decision-making processes. Researchers from the HEIs and YABs employed structured observation to record group dynamics and facilitation strategies. Youth reflected on their game design process by writing development logs o after each of the CGJ Kit phases, highlighting moments of agency, feedback and challenge. Finally, vox pops and short video testimonials captured first-person or team perspectives in real time.

After the CGJs, further surveys and collaborative reflections with youth and partners focused on how the outcomes, learnings, and collaboration could be improved for the next iteration. Each cultural hub documented the games created, including prototypes and development logs on the online platform itch.io. Reflection sprints with cultural hub teams synthesised insights and supported the refinement of subsequent CGJs.

Ethical considerations guided all research activities. Explicit ethical practices such as GDPR compliance, using a participant code for the surveys, and securing informed consent from all participants were utilised. Implicit considerations for facilitating participant agency over their experience in the CGJ were also practiced. For example, the Hilversum cultural hub practiced having a confidant on sight for participants to come to safely discuss any situations of discomfort or concern during the CGJ process. By addressing both formal procedural ethics as well addressing the more implicit and situational ethics, the project organisers strove to ensure that young people's contributions were respected and that participation remained inclusive and empowering.

3.2.1 Data Sources

The CGJs generated a rich and varied set of data. Quantitative sources included surveys completed before and after events, while qualitative sources ranged from observation notes

and values activities to voxpops, pitch recordings, and video testimonials. In addition, the game prototypes and their documentation on itch.io via development logs formed a vital part of the dataset, providing concrete artefacts for analysis. Media outputs such as photographs, video recordings, and cross-cultural hub Discord exchanges further contextualised the CGJs.

3.2.2 Local Analyses

Analysis was conducted at multiple levels. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise survey findings, offering insight into participants' learning, agency, and cultural engagement. Qualitative data materials were thematically coded in thematic analyses to trace how values, cultural heritage, and civic concerns were integrated into design processes. Particular attention was paid to how youth showed signs of empowered participation and exercised agency in the E-P-I-C phases.

Three complementary frameworks were developed to capture the different dimensions of practice: the **Event Case Study Analysis**, the **Local Thematic Analysis**, and the **Local Games Analysis**. The templates for these analyses can be found in the Appendix. Together, these frameworks provided a comprehensive understanding of how each of the twelve CGJs unfolded, how participants experienced them, and how cultural and societal values were expressed through the games created.

The **Event Case Study Analysis** documented each CGJ as a detailed case, focusing on its local context, organisational structure, facilitation approach, and cross-sectoral collaboration within the Quadruple Helix model. Using a shared template, researchers captured what happened before, during, and after each CGJ, identifying key moments, tensions, and outcomes. This method ensured that each cultural hub's distinct setting, resources, and dynamics were systematically recorded while enabling later cross-case comparison.

The **Local Thematic Analysis** provided a deeper interpretive layer by examining the data produced across interviews, observations, devlogs, vox pops, and visual materials. Following Braun and Clarke's reflexive thematic analysis framework, researchers combined deductive codes derived from EPIC-WE's research questions with inductive codes emerging from local data. This approach revealed common strategies for youth engagement, recurring challenges in balancing structure and creativity, and diverse approaches to embedding cultural values in game-making.

Finally, the **Local Games Analysis** examined the games themselves as cultural artefacts and expressions of collective meaning-making. Using a shared analysis protocol, each cultural hub assessed a representative set of prototypes created during the CGJs, exploring

their mechanics, narratives, values, and social themes. This analysis made it possible to trace how local heritage, cultural contexts, and societal concerns were translated into gameplay, and how these reflected broader European values.

Together, these three layers of analysis created an integrated view of the CGJs allowing WP4 to document the results of implementing the protocols designed and delivered by WP3. Further, after the first round of interventions, these local analyses also generated empirical insights that directly informed the redesign and strengthening of WP3 tasks and outcomes for the second round of CGJs. This iterative process between design, experimentation, analysis, and redesign became central to how WP3 and WP4 evolved together, reinforcing the EPIC-WE project's emphasis on learning through doing.

3.3 Data Used for this Deliverable

By integrating practical protocols, research instruments, and multi-level analysis, each CGJ is able to be studied as a distinct case while also contributing to a cumulative understanding across cultural hubs. For this specific report, we have relied primarily on the 12 local case studies produced by each cultural hub for their CGJs. Some input from the games analysis and thematic analysis have been used to shape the reflections and implications at the end of this report.¹

3.3.1 Structure of CGJ Case Studies

Each of the 12 CGJ case studies that follow is organised according to a consistent structure, ensuring comparability while capturing local context sensitivity. Each case study includes:

1. A short summary of the CGJ, including date, location, and theme;
2. A list of participating sectors (CHI, CI, HEI, YCs) and their roles;
3. An overview of the CGJ planning process used and recruitment strategies;
4. Details on how intangible cultural heritage (European values) and tangible cultural heritage (artworks, archives, sites, collections, etc.) were integrated, the process with CGJ Kit and its E-P-I-C phases, research and documentation methods used, and two examples of games through/for culture prototypes produced by YCs during the CGJ;
5. Feedback from participants, successes and challenges identified by cultural hub partners and through the implementation of the research protocol.

¹ The datasets generated during the current study are available from the project coordinator on reasonable request.

DBR Round 1 - Local Cultural Game Jams

04

4. DBR Round 1 – Local Cultural Game Jams

The first round of CGJs (February–September 2024) marked the initial application of the D3.1, CGJ framework and CGJ Kit (Protocol 2) and its accompanying practical (Protocol 4) and research (Protocol 3) protocols. This round tested the E-P-I-C process model, transition tools, and CGJ methods along with youth recruitment, facilitation, and evaluation across three European QH Cultural Hubs: Aarhus (Denmark), Óbidos (Portugal), and Hilversum (Netherlands). Each cultural hub hosted two local CGJs, working within their own cultural heritage collections, sites, and contexts and with their local quadruple helix partners (CHI, CI, HEI, and youth). The aim of this first DBR round was not only to test the innovated CGJ framework and Kit and its associated D3.1 protocols but also to generate early insights on youth empowerment, partner collaboration, and the integration of cultural heritage and European values into the game-making as culture-making process. The six CGJs provided critical data for DBR, enabling refinements to the CGJ framework, CGJ Kit and informing the glocal interventions to take place in DBR Round 2 (using the D3.2 protocol 1-4).

The first six local CGJs included:

- **Aarhus CGJ1 (February 2–4, 2024):** Centred on *Human Nature*, drawing on ARoS Museum’s permanent cultural heritage exhibition of philosophy, religion, exploration, and landscape to inspire games through/for culture connected to European values;
- **Aarhus CGJ2 (September 7–8, 2024):** Focused on post-1960 contemporary art from the cultural heritage exhibition *ARoS Collection: 1960 - now*, with participants reflecting on modern identity, culture, and European values;
- **Óbidos CGJ1 (February 6–9, 2024):** Inspired by Óbidos’s recognition as a cultural heritage site (UNESCO City of Literature), participants created games through/for culture that celebrated literary heritage and engaged with European values;
- **Óbidos CGJ2 (April 29–May 2, 2024):** Addressed sustainability by engaging with the cultural heritage site of the Óbidos Lagoon and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially Goals 14 and 15 (Life Below Water and Life on Land);
- **Hilversum CGJ1 (April 13–14, 2024):** Allowed participants to define their own cultural heritage themes, linking them to European values while drawing inspiration from the Sound and Vision Museum’s cultural heritage exhibition;
- **Hilversum CGJ2 (September 9–13, 2024):** Worked with local schools to focus on *Media and Democracy* and *Media and Equality*, exploring cultural heritage values through the lens of civic participation and representation.

Together, these six CGJs demonstrated how CGJs could be adapted to different cultural heritage collections, sites, sector needs, and youth participants, while still following a shared CGJ framework and Kit.

4.1 Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ1 (Winter 2024)

Figure1, Participants prototyping during the Aarhus CGJ1.
Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, February 2024. Used with permission.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ1, Human Nature)

- Date:** February 3–4, 2024
- Location:** ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark
- Duration:** 2 days
- Participants:** 23 youth (ages 15–27, open recruitment)
- Number of Games:** 5 prototypes
- Theme:** Human Nature (Golden Age artworks from ARoS’ permanent collection)

Table 2: Overview of Aarhus CGJ1

4.1.1 Introduction

The first Aarhus CGJ took place on February 3–4, 2024, inside the permanent exhibition [Human Nature](#) at ARoS, Scandinavia’s most visited art museum and CHI partner of EPIC-WE. *Human Nature* presents an exploration of the human condition through themes of philosophy, religion, exploration, and landscape, inviting visitors to reflect on humanity’s

relationship with nature and technology in a changing world. This curatorial framing provided a rich context for the CGJ, where twenty-three youth participants were encouraged to reinterpret selected artworks as interactive, playable experiences. Working directly within the exhibition space, surrounded by the artworks themselves, participants created five original game prototypes that translated visual art into participatory and narrative forms.

4.1.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Aarhus University (AU):** Led planning and coordination, conducted research during the CGJ, facilitated activities during the event, and managed pre- and post-event communication.
- **ARoS Aarhus Art Museum (ARoS):** Assisted with CGJ planning, handled all practical arrangements and on-the-spot tasks, and coordinated communication before and after the event.
- **Filmby Aarhus (AAKS):** Participated in CGJ planning, managed the Discord and Itch.io platforms, was responsible for event photography, managed pre- and post-event communication, and was responsible for recruitment.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Included coding experts (Coding Pirates), game developers (Funday Games), AU researchers, and ARoS Head of Public Engagement.
- **Coding Pirates:** Provided feedback, facilitated coding support, and contributed to the Expert Council and Expo (during the event).
- **Fun Day Games:** Gave a talk, offered feedback, assisted with programming, contributed to the Expert Council and Expo, and provided additional help as needed (during the event)

4.1.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation for the CGJ was organised through short, efficient cultural hub meetings inspired by design sprints, with clear divisions of roles and responsibility. The CGJ team built a **pilot CGJ in late 2023** (a six-hour CGJ session with 40 high school students), which tested the pilot materials and workflows. Lessons from this pilot shaped preparation of the first version of the CGJ Kit, streamlining how participants received instructions and scaffolding.

Over 30 youth signed up for the CGJ1 through open **recruitment** led by Filmby Aarhus (AAKS), with 23 completing the CGJ1. Participants ranged in age from 15–27 and came from diverse educational and cultural backgrounds (audio design, visual art, programming, escape room design, cultural studies, aesthetics, dramaturgy, and animation). Teams were carefully put together to balance age, gender, disciplines, skills, and interests, with English set as the language of the CGJ.

Figure 2, Ideation Wheel and other facilitation materials from Aarhus CGJ1.

Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, February 2024. Used with permission.

4.1.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The CGJ was rooted in AROS's *Human Nature* exhibition, where participants explored artworks representing humanity's search for meaning across time. The four themed rooms of Philosophy, Religion, Exploration, and Landscape provided inspiration for game concepts, prompting reflection on how humans become and belong across different contexts. European values were integrated into the CGJ Kit and the CGJ brief, and they were highlighted during facilitation at key moments. Stand out tools included a **Cultural Safari** (artwalk and immersive exploration of artworks) and the **Ideation Wheel** (connecting cultural themes, European values, and game types). However, compared to the engagement with tangible cultural heritage (i.e. the artworks), the integration of intangible cultural heritage (i.e. European values) played a lighter role in shaping design decisions.

Schedule & Structure

The two-day format was designed to balance cultural exploration, creative ideation, and hands-on prototyping of games through and for culture. The Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ1 followed the **EPIC-WE CGJ Kit** process, progressing through the phases of *Experience*, *Play*, *Imagine*, and *Create*, each with tailored design methods and transition tools.

- **Day 1 (February 3):** Welcome and *Experience* phase artwalk (tour in the museum exhibition), inspiration talks from sector experts (games, culture, value-sensitive

D4.1 Report on Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions

design),), *Play* phase (ideation and game concept development), Expert Council feedback, and *Imagine* (mockups and prototyping), followed by overnight *Create* work to have playable games through and for culture for the concluding Games Expo.

- **Day 2 (February 4):** Brunch and preparation, continued *Create* phase (final development of games through and for culture), and a public CGJ Games EXPO where the CGJ teams pitched and showcased their games.

Participant Engagement

YCs engaged with the CGJ as both informal learners of game-making and cultural co-creators. They demonstrated agency in their design decisions, from interpreting artworks to shaping prototypes in collaborative teams. The diverse mix of skills, ranging from art and storytelling to programming and sound, ensured that each participant could contribute meaningfully, while the use of transition tools such as the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council reinforced active decision-making. Participants valued the opportunity to reinterpret art and heritage in playful formats, to network with peers, and to test their creative abilities in a supportive but intensive environment. Organisers noted that agency was particularly visible in how participants integrated cultural material into new forms, bridging personal perspectives with collective creativity.

Research Methods

- Pre/post surveys
- Semi-structured interviews (before and after CGJ)
- Vox pop interviews
- Participatory observation and field notes
- Visual ethnography and documentation boards
- Game logs uploaded to itch.io

Documentation

Extensive documentation included professional photography by ARoS/AAKS, recorded expert sessions and feedback, and team-produced devlogs on Itch.io. Five prototypes were uploaded online, though supporting consistent student documentation remained a challenge.

While only a portion of games were fully polished, the prototypes reflected strong engagement with cultural heritage, values, and artistic interpretation. The EXPO showcase highlighted both the creative ambition of participants and the capacity of CGJs to foster new ways of connecting art and play.

4.1.5 Outcomes

The Games:

All five games through/for culture from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Aarhus CGJ1](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Aarhus CGJ1](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Goose on the Loose: A calm, exploratory game inspired by philosophical artworks, embodying the European value of **freedom**. It invites players into a child's imaginative world of peace and reflection, contrasting unfairness in the real world with an aesthetic of solace.

Roomination: Inspired by Vilhelm Hammershøi's paintings, this eerie game explores the cultural value of **freedom** by confronting players with enclosed spaces, prolonged introspection, and the limits of choice, offering a slow, unsettling meditation on personal rumination.

Table 3: Two example games from Aarhus CGJ1

Participant Feedback

Feedback from participants highlighted both the creative and social value of the CGJ. Many students appreciated the opportunity to meet new people and build a sense of community through shared creative work. One participant explained: *"I had been looking for ways to meet more people in this city, and I thought the Game Jam would be an interesting way to do this while combining my interests."*

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Others emphasised the unique combination of art and games, valuing the chance to reinterpret cultural heritage through playful forms: *“It’s really just a cool experience to come up with and make a fun game based on struggles or good values in our society.”*

Signs of learning and empowered participation were also evident. Participants reflected on how the CGJ supported skill development, collaboration, and personal growth within an intensive format. As one student remarked: *“I feel like I personally learned a lot... time management, what I know about art, who I am able to collaborate effectively with.”*

Figure 3, Ideation Wheel and other facilitation materials from Aarhus CGJ1.
Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, February 2024. Used with permission.

Successes

- **Youth empowered participation** was strong, with participants developing meaningful cultural heritage reflections and hands-on skills while linking games to cultural heritage;
- **Quadruple helix cultural hub collaboration** flourished, with art professionals, game developers, and students working together as co-creators;
- **Innovative reinterpretations of tangible cultural heritage** emerged, extending artworks into interactive cultural formats that inspired new cultural expressions.

Challenges

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- **Documentation requirements** such as devlogs and ethical paperwork disrupted creative flow and were perceived as burdensome;
- **Expert Council timing** reduced its impact, as arriving nine hours into the CGJ left teams reluctant to pivot after coding had already begun;
- **Balancing research and participant experience** caused tension, highlighting the need to simplify paperwork, streamline facilitation, and integrate youth more fully into planning.

4.2 Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ2 (Summer 2024)

Figure 4, Participants touring the ARoS Collection: 1960 - now during the Aarhus CGJ2. Note. Photograph by Amalie Bech-Willumsen, September 2024. Used with permission.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ2, ARoS Collection: 1960-now)

Date: September 7–8, 2024

Location: ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 2 days

Participants: 39 youth participants (open recruitment plus one secondary school class)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes

Theme: Contemporary and postmodern artworks, ARoS Collection: 1960 - now

Table 4: Overview of Aarhus CGJ2

4.2.1 Introduction

The second CGJ in Aarhus, Denmark (CGJ2) brought together 39 youth participants for a weekend of co-creating games rooted in cultural heritage on September 7–8, 2024. Hosted at ARoS, participants explored and drew inspiration from tangible cultural heritage within the modern era, reinterpreting artworks through innovative game-making that reflected and engaged with the heritage collections. The Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ2 focused on

contemporary and postmodern artworks within *ARoS Collection: 1960 - now*, with museum facilitators guiding participants through interpretation and cultural reflection.

4.2.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Aarhus University (AU):** Planning, coordination, research, facilitation, pre and post-event communication;
- **ARoS Art Museum (ARoS):** Venue, cultural expertise, art tours, logistics, and security;
- **Filmby Aarhus (AAKS):** Recruitment, communication, Discord and Itch.io management, photography, technical support;
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Contributed to CGJ planning, led revisions of the CGJ Kit, and took a primary role in facilitation during the event;
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Included coding experts (Coding Pirates), game developers (Funday Games), YAB members, an AU researcher, and ARoS Registrar;
- **Coding Pirates:** Provided feedback, facilitated coding support, and contributed to the Expert Council and Expo (during the event);
- **Fair Games:** Offered feedback, assisted with programming, contributed to the Expert Council and Expo, and provided additional help as needed (during the event).

4.2.3 Planning and Preparation

Aarhus CGJ2 was collaboratively developed through a series of short, design sprint-inspired cultural hub meetings. Aarhus University coordinated planning and research, ARoS handled venue logistics and communication, and AAKS managed recruitment, digital platforms, and documentation. A key innovation was the active involvement of the Youth Advisory Board: one member co-facilitated the Aarhus CGJ2 event and helped revise the CGJ Kit, slowing the pace and making activities more inclusive and accessible for youth participants.

Recruitment combined open registration with targeted outreach. A YAB member and AAKS worked directly with educational institutions, bringing in 16 students from an upper secondary innovation class, while additional participants joined through ARoS's newsletter and social media. The final group of 39 participants represented a mix of first-time game-makers and experienced makers across analogue and digital formats, with teams intentionally formed to balance skills and perspectives.

Figure 5, Participants collaborating during Aarhus CGJ2.

Note. Photograph by Amalie Bech-Willumsen, September 2024. Used with permission.

4.2.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

Intangible cultural heritage in the form of European values were introduced through the CGJ Kit, the CGJ brief, and CGJ facilitation prompts. While values played a less prominent role than the artworks themselves, they framed discussion during key activities. Cultural heritage engagement was anchored in *ARoS Collection: 1960 - now*, with art professionals guiding participants to connect artistic themes to playable concepts.

Schedule and Structure

- **Day 1 (September 7):** Welcome, icebreakers, art walk, Experience, Play, Expert Council, and Imagine phases;
- **Day 2 (September 8):** Breakfast and check-in, Playtest and Imagine, Create, pitches, and a public Games EXPO showcase.

Participant Engagement

Engagement was scaffolded through Discord pre-boarding and a Youth Advisory Board-led icebreaker. Teams were formed in the beginning by AAKs aiming to mix skills and backgrounds. The facilitation rhythm was intentionally slower and more inclusive, allowing space for questions, reflection, and private breaks where needed. Youth agency was visible

in how participants interpreted artworks, chose mechanics, and iterated on feedback from mentors and the Expert Council.

Research Methods

- Pre and post-surveys;
- Vox pop qualitative interviews;
- Participatory observations and field notes;
- Visual ethnography and community boards;
- Research through design.

Documentation

The CGJ was documented with professional photography, recorded feedback sessions, and team uploads on itch.io.

Nine prototypes were shared online, though documentation by participants remained uneven. The EXPO allowed teams to present games to peers, facilitators, and guests.

4.2.5 Outcomes

The Games

All nine games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Aarhus CGJ2](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Aarhus CGJ2](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

<p>Metamorphosis: A platformer about self-discovery that explores cultural diversity, allowing players to explore personal growth and identity through imaginative environments and encounters with “Doubt-Monsters.”</p>	<p>Grind the World: A symbolic, choice-driven game inspired by contemporary artwork, reflecting on freedom of expression. It challenges players to reflect on ethics, identity, and absurdity through playful but thought-provoking grinding mechanics.</p>
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Table 5: Two example games from Aarhus CGJ2

Participant Feedback

Participants emphasised both the social and creative value of the CGJ. Many saw it as a chance to collaborate, connect with peers, and explore new approaches to game-making, noting how valuable it was to see how others think about games and art. Others highlighted the collaborative spirit and inclusive processes, appreciating the freedom to experiment and merge art with play in surprising ways.

Suggestions focused on practical improvements. Several felt the Expert Council should be integrated earlier to provide guidance during idea generation and then return later for refinement. Others called for more tailored facilitation and clearer support for beginners and analogue-focused teams to ensure everyone had accessible entry points.

Figure 6, Participants working during Aarhus CGJ2.

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Note. Photograph by Amalie Bech-Willumsen, September 2024. Used with permission.

Successes

- **Youth participation and empowerment** were strengthened by Discord pre-boarding and Youth Advisory Board-led icebreakers, which supported active collaboration and creative ownership in cultural heritage;
- **Cultural hub partner cross-sector collaboration** was efficient, with clearly defined roles and agile meetings enabling smooth planning and delivery;
- **Integration of tangible and intangible cultural heritage (artworks & European values)** was achieved through curated art tours and Expert Council feedback, grounding game design in cultural artefacts and values-based discussion.

Challenges

- **Logistical preparation** created friction, with interviews and consent processes slowing down the event; earlier communication and documentation were needed;
- **Inclusivity in facilitation** fell short, as beginners and analogue makers needed more structured support; differentiated facilitation and simplified tools are recommended;
- **Consent protocols** for participants under 18 caused delays, underscoring the need for streamlined systems that balance compliance with youth autonomy.

4.3 Óbidos Cultural Hub CGJ1 (Winter 2024)

Figure 7, During the cultural visit to “Mercado Biológico”, where they sell bio fruits and vegetables but also second hand books.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ1, UNESCO City of Literature)

Date: February 6–9, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 26 youth (ages 18–28)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (one made by Professors from Lusófona University)

Theme: Óbidos as UNESCO City of Literature

Table 6: Overview of Óbidos CGJ1

4.3.1 Introduction

The first Óbidos CGJ (CGJ1) was held on February 6–9, 2024 in the historic town of Óbidos, Portugal. Over the course of four days, 26 young participants collaborated with facilitators, cultural experts, and game industry professionals to create nine original prototypes. Inspired by Óbidos’s UNESCO designation as a City of Literature, CGJ1 sought to reflect on the role of literature and books to enrich our cultural experiences into playful, interactive experiences.

Unlike shorter formats at other cultural hubs, this was a four-day residential CGJ, where participants lived, shared meals, and worked together in a shared creative space. CGJ1 combined lectures, cultural visits, creative workshops, and intensive prototyping.

D4.1 Report on Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions

Participants drew inspiration from the medieval setting, bookshops, libraries, and literary history of Óbidos, blending local culture with European values in their games. The event concluded with a public showcase where games were presented to peers, facilitators, and local stakeholders such as the Mayor of Óbidos, followed by a reflective roundtable.

4.3.2 Partners / People Involved

CGJ1 was organised and delivered by the Óbidos cultural hub partners, each contributing with distinct expertise:

- **Óbidos Municipality (CMO):** Provided the cultural heritage site, accommodation, meals, logistical support, and cultural heritage programming (lectures, guided tour of the town). Defined the theme “Óbidos as a UNESCO City of Literature”;
- **Lusófona University (LU):** Co-organiser responsible for recruitment, research design, and documentation. Adapted CGJ ideation methods, structured the timeline, and facilitated game-making activities;
- **Battlesheep (BS):** Creative industry partner, co-organiser, and facilitator. Supported participants in technical aspects of prototyping and game-making;
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Game-making experts from UL and BS and cultural experts from CMO.

Additional presence included a communications intern for media coverage, local journalists reporting for regional newspapers, and a visit from the Mayor of Óbidos.

4.3.3 Planning and Preparation

The planning focused on defining the theme, structuring the agenda, and preparing recruitment and research instruments. The Óbidos Municipality proposed the theme in line with its cultural strategy, while Lusófona University coordinated research and recruitment. Battlesheep contributed to the design of the facilitation approach and provided technical expertise. Youth participants were not included in planning at this stage, with their role confined to the CGJ itself.

Recruitment was managed by Lusófona University through its videogame course networks. Dissemination took place via the official Discord server and a Google Form. Selection considered order of registration, gender balance, and prior experience in CGJs. Although 39 registered, 26 ultimately participated. All participants were university students aged 18-28, from videogames bachelor's. Recruitment successfully attracted motivated youth but lacked high school students and gender diversity.

Figure 8, Pre-game jam session with VNA ideation tool from Óbidos CGJ1.

4.3.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

European values were present but less foregrounded than cultural heritage. Instead, the emphasis laid on the literary and cultural identity of Óbidos. The integration of culture took place primarily through **pre-CGJ activities**: a lecture on Óbidos as a literary town, curated online materials, and a VNA (Values, Needs, Actions) ideation exercise. The pre-CGJ activities ended with a final guided cultural tour of bookshops, the medieval castle, a typography, and a gallery. These experiences strongly shaped both the visual style and mechanics of the games, grounding prototypes in lived cultural encounters.

Schedule & Structure

Rather than relying on the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, the cultural hub used existing expertise in game jam organisation. A VNA (Values, Needs, Actions) variation was tested during the pre-CGJ ideation workshop, encouraging participants to reflect on cultural values before entering the CGJ. The Reid et al. (2020) framework guided planning, structuring the process into four phases: Problem Space, CGJ Design, CGJ Delivery, and Follow-On Opportunities.

- **Pre-CGJ (January 9)**: Online lecture, ideation exercise and surveys;
- **Day 1 (February 6)**: Arrival in Óbidos, guided cultural visit, team formation, research tasks and first pitches;
- **Day 2 (February 7)**: Iterative development, interviews, pitches, mentoring and autonomous work;
- **Day 3 (February 8)**: Continued game-making, mayor's visit and evening showcase;

- **Day 4 (February 9):** Final deliveries, post-mortem roundtable, reflective discussion and departure.

Participant Engagement

YCs demonstrated strong collaboration, dividing tasks based on their skills. Teams were self-organised, with autonomy in project scope, workflow, and creative direction. Within this structure, participants managed their own time, leading design and prototyping processes largely independently. Pitches and interim critiques encouraged participants to reflect on cultural integration and refine their designs. However, youth had little agency in shaping the overarching theme or methodological framework, which were defined in advance.

Research Methods

- Pre- and post-surveys;
- Observation grids (daily tracking of interactions, behaviours);
- Vox pops (survey on expectations and reflections);
- Semi-structured interviews during the CGJ;
- Game analysis instrument applied to the YCs.

Documentation

Óbidos CGJ1 was extensively documented through photos and videos captured across all four days, alongside gameplay recordings of each prototype. Daily social media updates, particularly on Instagram, provided ongoing glimpses into the process, while a dedicated YouTube video offered a recap of the full event. In addition, two news articles in the local press highlighted the cultural and educational significance of the CGJ, helping to share its outcomes with a broader audience.

4.3.5 Outcomes

The Games

All nine games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Óbidos CGJ1](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Óbidos CGJ1](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Puss in Books: A typing-based adventure that celebrates the European value of cultural diversity, drawing on literary heritage and inviting players to “write” their own story as a cat exploring hidden tales in a library.

In Search for Words: A narrative exploration game set in Óbidos, reflecting the European value of freedom of expression, where players guide a writer through creative blocks by finding inspiration in the literary village.

Table 7: Two example games from Óbidos CGJ1

Participant Feedback

Participant evaluations showed high levels of satisfaction: 92% reported that their expectations were met or exceeded. Many highlighted how the medieval atmosphere of Óbidos contributed directly to creativity. Unlike typical game jams, participants valued the opportunity to step outside, take walks, and draw inspiration from the environment. One participant noted: *“It was much better here, the atmosphere, getting out of here, visiting the village, taking a stroll. It gave me ideas I would never have had just staying in a classroom.”*

Others emphasised how the cultural visits inspired mechanics and storytelling. A participant explained: *“Almost all of our ideas came directly from something we saw on the first day in the bookshops, the castle, the typography workshop. It made the theme come alive.”*

Several participants reflected on skill development, pointing to improved teamwork, time management, and pitching skills. For some, this was their first experience in a structured game jam, and they appreciated the opportunity to test their abilities in a supportive but intensive environment. At the same time, challenges were noted. Some found the theme “City of Literature” too abstract until the cultural visits gave it tangible meaning. A number of participants also mentioned the lack of diversity in the cohort, particularly the absence of high school students, which limited perspectives. Others expressed a desire for greater

youth involvement in setting the theme and design methods, arguing that this would create stronger ownership.

Figure 9, One of the teams presenting their game in the showcase during Óbidos CGJ1.

Successes

- **Immersive cultural heritage setting:** The town of Óbidos directly inspired game mechanics, visuals, and storytelling, making cultural engagement authentic and tangible;
- **Reflective cultural heritage pitching:** Interim pitch sessions encouraged participants to critically evaluate cultural heritage integration, adjusting scope and focus;
- **Pre-CGJ preparation:** Lectures, ideation exercises, and guided tours grounded participants in the cultural heritage theme and enriched creativity.

Challenges

- **Abstract theme:** “UNESCO City of Literature” was too vague at first, and only became meaningful through cultural visits;
- **Recruitment gaps:** Gender balance and representation of younger participants were weak, reducing diversity;
- **Limited youth agency:** While autonomous in teams, participants had no role in defining the theme or agenda, limiting empowered participation.

4.4 Óbidos Cultural Hub CGJ2 (Summer 2024)

Figure 10, Participants working during Óbidos CGJ2.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ2, Óbidos Lagoon)

Date: April 29 – May 2, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 40 participants (25 university students, 15 secondary school students, ages 15–25)

Number of Games: 14 prototypes

Theme: Sustainability and Biodiversity – Óbidos Lagoon, connecting to SDGs 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land)

Table 8: Overview of Óbidos CGJ2

4.4.1 Introduction

The second CGJ in Óbidos (CGJ2) took place from April 29 to May 2, 2024, bringing together 40 young participants to design games inspired by the biodiversity of the Óbidos Lagoon. The event focused on raising awareness of sustainability and environmental

stewardship by embedding the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the design process. Pre-CGJ activities were held in March and April, including an online informational session, an expert lecture about the SDGs and biodiversity, and a guided lagoon visit led by local cultural and biodiversity experts. The participants worked intensively for four days at the Creativity square, producing 14 digital prototypes.

4.4.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Óbidos Municipality (CHI):** Provided the cultural heritage site, logistics (accommodation, meals, equipment), defined the cultural heritage theme, and facilitated cultural heritage activities (lecture and lagoon visit). Three cultural facilitators supported participants throughout the event;
- **Lusófona University (HEI):** Co-organiser responsible for research, data collection, recruitment, and workshop facilitation. Five facilitators and two researchers supported the CGJ
- **Battlesheep (CI):** Creative industry partner acting as co-organiser and facilitator;
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Game-making experts from UL and BS and cultural experts from CMO.
- **Participant Support:** Five secondary school teachers support their students during the CGJ.

4.4.3 Planning and Preparation

The planning was managed collaboratively between the three cultural hub partners. Tasks included designing the agenda, defining the theme, setting research instruments, and managing logistics. Unlike the first CGJ, facilitators committed to full participation across pre-CGJ activities and the main event, ensuring consistent feedback. Youth participants were not directly involved in pre-planning of this second CGJ.

LU recruited university participants (videogame bachelor students) via Discord and Google Forms. Selection considered registration order, age, and gender balance. Josefa de Óbidos Secondary School recruited 15 students through teacher selection from a vocational programme. While effective, this lacked transparency regarding the selection criteria used by teachers and left some students feeling obliged to attend.

Based on the feedback from participants of the first CGJ, the CGJ Kit was adapted:

- An **information kit** with background on the lagoon and SDGs was distributed;
- A **Unity framework** (“Óbidos Lagoon Adventure Framework”) was pre-built to support high school participants with limited coding experience;

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- A **VNA-based ideation tool** (Verbs, Nouns, Adjectives) was used to generate cultural-creative directions;
- A **mood board** inspired thematic and visual choices.

Figure 11, Cultural facilitators assisting the participants with feedback on their games during Óbidos CGJ2.

4.4.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

SDGs 14 and 15 were positioned as cultural values framing the CGJ. Facilitators embedded these values through a lecture, a lagoon visit, and continuous guidance during development. Participants explored biodiversity, migratory birds, local species, and sustainable fishing practices. This grounded global sustainability goals in a tangible, local ecosystem.

Schedule and Structure

- **Pre-CGJ (March–April):** Online logistics session (March 27), SDG & biodiversity lecture (April 12), and guided lagoon visit (April 15);
- **Day 1 (April 29):** Icebreakers, Unity workshop, VNA ideation, team formation, and first pitches;
Day 2 (April 30): Game-making, interviews, and facilitator check-ins;
- **Day 3 (May 1):** Midpoint reflection, screenshot submission, and playtesting;

- **Day 4 (May 2):** Final development, showcase, post-mortem roundtable.

Participant Engagement & Empowerment

Lusófona students were confident and self-directed, while high school participants required more structured encouragement. Facilitators, both cultural and technical, visited teams regularly to provide feedback. Though participants had no say in the theme or values, they retained autonomy in forming teams, assigning roles, and shaping design choices. Pitch sessions provided valuable moments of dialogue and agency.

Support & Facilitation

- Cultural facilitators shared ecological and historical details of the lagoon, ensuring accurate thematic integration;
- HEI and CI facilitators provided support on game design, development tools, and implementation of game mechanics;
- Teachers supported secondary students with supervision and encouragement.

This dual cultural and technical facilitation model was highly valued by participants.

Research Methods

- Pre- and post-surveys (with demographic, cultural, and SDG-focused sections);
- Observations (structured grid tracking space, youth engagement, facilitation, empowerment);
- Vox-pop style interviews with participants, teachers, and facilitators;
- Game analysis using five categories: innovation, playfulness, educational value, cultural impact, and viability.
- Itch.io uploads with screenshots, videos, and descriptions for each prototype.

Documentation

The CGJ was captured through photos, videos, gameplay recordings, social media posts, and a news story published via CICANT (Lusófona's Centre for Research in Applied Communication, Culture, and New Technologies), HEI-LAB (Lusófona's Digital Human-environment Interaction Lab) and partner websites.

4.4.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 14 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Óbidos CGJ2](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Óbidos CGJ2](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Criminal Fauna Identification: A detective-style game where players must identify which bird species committed a “crime” by analysing habits and characteristics. The game reflected values of **justice**, **knowledge-sharing**, and **biodiversity awareness**.

Óbidos Watching: Players act as a park ranger tasked with protecting the lagoon from human and environmental threats (littering, disruptive tourism) while photographing local species. Values expressed include **environmental stewardship**, **responsibility**, and **respect for nature**.

Table 9: Two example games from Óbidos CGJ2

Participant Feedback

Most Lusófona participants felt their expectations were met (92%), while high school students reported a less positive outcome (47% “met,” 47% “exceeded”). Pre-CGJ activities were rated as essential by nearly all participants (97.5%), with the lagoon visit described as the most inspiring element for integrating cultural knowledge into their games.

University students valued the freedom to experiment and the collaborative spirit of the CGJ, while high school students highlighted the novelty of hands-on cultural experiences outside the classroom. Feedback also pointed to challenges, including hardware performance for some groups, limited integration between school and university teams, and surveys that were not fully adapted to younger participants.

Figure 12, Participants presenting their game to the public in the showcase during Óbidos CGJ2.

Successes

- **Pre-CGJ preparation created stronger cultural heritage foundations**, giving participants time to absorb cultural insights before development of their game through/for culture;
- **Continuous facilitation enhanced cultural heritage accuracy and creativity**, with cultural and technical experts ensuring games remained thematically grounded;
- **Inclusion of high school students diversified participation**, expanding the educational scope and age representation of the CGJ.

Challenges

- **Technical limitations hampered learning**, as many high school students' computers could not run Unity effectively, delaying workshops;
- **Limited collaboration between student groups**, with high school and university participants working separately rather than integrating;
- **Youth exclusion from theme-setting and planning** restricted empowered participation, echoing challenges from the first CGJ.

4.5 Hilversum Cultural Hub CGJ1 (Spring 2024)

Figure 13, Participants playing in the Media Museum during Hilversum CGJ1.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ1, Open Choice)

- Date:** April 13–14, 2024
- Location:** Media Museum, Hilversum, Netherlands
- Duration:** 2 days
- Participants:** 15 participants, open recruitment
- Number of Games:** 4 prototypes
- Theme:** Open choice

Table 10: Overview of Hilversum CGJ1

4.5.1 Introduction

The first Hilversum CGJ was held on April 13–14, 2024 at the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV) [Media Museum](#). Over two days, 15 youth participants created games inspired by the museum’s media collection and by European values. Unlike the other

cultural hubs, this CGJ began without a fixed theme. Instead, participants defined their own cultural or societal issues and connected them to European values, supported by an EUjia board designed by the research team at Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) as a facilitation tool. This approach prioritised agency, creativity, and personal relevance, positioning youth as cultural co-creators.

4.5.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV):** Lead production, facilitated access to the cultural collection, led communication activities, and assisted with recruitment support.
- **Dropstuff Media (DM):** Led the creative and technical facilitation, helping participants shape ideas into playable prototypes.
- **Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS):** Oversaw research activities, recruitment, and documentation.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Included two game industry experts from the Dutch Games Association and Control Magazine, two independent game designers, one arts and culture expert from Utrecht University of the Arts, and two serious games researchers from TU Delft.

4.5.3 Planning and Preparation

Planning was coordinated through design sprints among NISV, DM, and AUAS, combining online and in-person meetings. Teams were organised around four areas: recruitment, facilitation, logistics, and research. These teams often included members from multiple partner organisations. Although youth were not involved in the planning of this first CGJ, flexibility was built into the theme of the CGJ to maximise youth ownership during the event itself. The structure of the CGJ followed the four phases of the E-P-I-C process model from the GCJ Kit.

Recruitment followed an open call for 18–25 year olds. The recruitment strategy relied heavily on a mix of promotion toward personal network connections and cold reach out to universities, applied sciences, and vocational schools with programmes in game design, cultural studies, and creative business. Of 25 registrations, 15 participants attended. Most had limited prior experience with game design, but brought diverse creative skills and cultural perspectives that enriched collaboration.

Figure 14, EUjia board being used by participants during Hilversum CGJ1.

4.5.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The NISV collection displayed in its Media Museum provided a cultural heritage foundation, exposing participants to how media intersects with daily life through storytelling, news, shopping, and more. A highlight being the interactive games floor where participants could play through favorite childhood games like *Snake* and *Floor is Lava*. The cultural hub partners also developed and used an EUjia board to support participants in articulating issues and connect them to European values. This proved especially effective in helping participants to ground their games in both the tangible cultural heritage artefacts found in the museum and intangible cultural heritage in the form of European values. Additional creative warm-up activities, such as “30 Circles” and LEGO tower-building, helped spark ideation and build team cohesion.

Schedule and Structure

The two-day, 48-hour CGJ followed the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, moving participants through the four phases of Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. Many of the recommended research and practical protocol activities were tested, leading to quite agenda of exercises for the participants to follow:

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- **Day 1 (April 13):** Welcoming + paperwork, EUija Board exercise to become familiar with EU Values, tour of the Media Museum, creative warm-up exercises, Expert Council, and late-night pizza and prototyping
- **Day 2 (April 14):** Playtest sessions for iteration and final pitches and jury

Participant Engagement

Youth participants were given considerable freedom to form teams, define themes, and decide whether to create digital or analogue games. This autonomy was well received but at times overwhelming, particularly given the number of brainstorming and ideation activities. While some participants thrived under this structure, others expressed a desire for more time to focus on making their games.

Research Methods

- Pre- and post-surveys
- Observational notes by two researchers
- Voxpop-style interviews in a recording space
- Playtest videos documenting prototypes in development

Documentation of the CGJ

The event was documented extensively through photographs, recorded expert sessions, and observation boards placed in participant areas for real-time feedback. These outputs not only preserved the process for communication but also supported later analysis.

4.5.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 4 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Hilversum CGJ1](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Hilversum CGJ1](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Nijntje Goes Back to School: A narrative-driven game exploring the European value of **human dignity**, with a focus on mental health, empathy, and community support, where players help Nijntje (Miffy in English) navigate emotional challenges and promote resilience through collective care.

CAT-a-strophic Climate: A playful yet educational game embodying the European value of **rule of law**, where players become heroic cats cleaning plastic from the ocean, highlighting both the urgency of environmental action and the responsibility to uphold stronger protections for the planet.

Table 11: Two example games from Hilversum CGJ1

Participant Feedback

Feedback highlighted the CGJ’s empowering aspects, particularly the chance to work with real cultural heritage material and connect design decisions to European values. However, some participants felt that too many brainstorming methods detracted from time available to fully develop their games. Multiple participants shared that they wanted more time to work on their game rather than participate in structured activities.

Figure 15, Participants participating in creative brainstorming activities during *Hilversum CGJ1*.

Successes

- **Cross-sector cultural hub collaboration** between CHI, CI, and HEI partners was effective, ensuring smooth organisation and delivery of the CGJ.
- **The Media Museum’s cultural heritage collection** served as a powerful cultural heritage catalyst, sparking meaningful and creative games through/for culture ideas.
- **The EUjia board** provided a practical tool to link participant-defined themes to European values, grounding the design process in cultural and civic reflection.

Challenges

- **Recruitment outcomes** were weaker than expected, resulting in fewer participants than planned.
- **Youth exclusion from planning** limited their ownership of the CGJ’s structure, reducing their influence on early design decisions.
- **Facilitation intensity** was high, with too many activities leaving participants feeling rushed during the game-making phase.

4.6 Hilversum Cultural Hub CGJ2 (Autumn 2024)

Figure 16, Participants presenting their game during the final pitches to an AUAS researcher and a YAB member during Hilversum CGJ2.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ2, Media, Democracy, and Equality)

Date: September 9–13, 2024
Location: X11 High School (Utrecht) & NISV Media Museum (Hilversum), Netherlands
Duration: 4 days, across one week
Participants: 61 secondary school students (ages 16–18)
Number of Games: 15 prototypes
Theme: Choice between Media & Democracy or Media & Equality

Table 12: Overview of Hilversum CGJ2

4.6.1 Introduction

The second Hilversum CGJ ran on September 9–13, 2024 and marked a significant expansion from the first event, both in scale and ambition. Hosted in collaboration with X11 secondary school in Utrecht and the Media Museum of NISV, it engaged 61 students across

three classes in a week-long process that blended classroom activities with cultural immersion. Unlike the open, small-scale format of the first CGJ, CGJ2 was deliberately embedded into a school programme, providing an opportunity to reach a much broader cohort of youth under 18. The themes “Media & Democracy” and “Media & Equality” were chosen in collaboration with teachers to connect directly to curricular goals.

4.6.2 Partners / People Involved

Hilversum cultural hub worked together with its newly instated Youth Advisory Board to manage the following CGJ activities:

- **Sound & Vision (NISV):** Provided cultural resources, hosted museum activities, and linked exhibits to European values.
- **Dropstuff Media (DM):** Led creative facilitation and design activities.
- **Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS):** Coordinated research, documentation, and evaluation.
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Provided advice in the development of the CGJ materials during design sprints, and joined as jury members, linking experiences across Hilversum's local CGJs.
- **X11 High School:** Provided the student cohort, classroom space, and some teacher support throughout the week.
- **Expert Council & Jury:** included 1 specialist in misinformation (DROG), 1 expert in immersive media (Improvive), 1 games industry expert (Control Magazine), and 4 YAB members.

4.6.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation for the second CGJ drew heavily on lessons learned from the first Hilversum CGJ. Structured design sprints between CHI, CI, HEI, and teachers replaced the more fragmented planning style of the first CGJ. A new **comprehensive handbook** consolidated activities, rules, and documentation into a single resource, addressing participant overwhelm from the first event.

In addition, **recruitment** shifted from open applications to a closed recruitment model, securing three entire classes from X11 high school. This ensured high participation numbers, though communication gaps meant some students and teachers arrived underprepared, requiring extra clarification during the opening sessions.

To better support students with little or no prior experience in game development, a Game Design 101 workshop was introduced on the first day. This session covered the basics of game mechanics, helping to level the playing field and build confidence among complete beginners before moving into the main CGJ activities. Another innovation was the

introduction of **formal roles**: Curator, Storyteller, Designer, Collector. These were assigned via a tarot card exercise. This method was intended to scaffold group work by encouraging students to specialise, though in practice many teams defaulted to sharing tasks equally.

Figure 17, the Game Jam handbook for Hilversum CGJ2.

4.6.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The themes of **Democracy** and **Equality** were explored during a full-day visit to the NISV Media Museum. Students were tasked with visiting different thematic floors, responding to prompts, and collecting cards as proof of engagement. While some groups connected their games to these cultural inputs, others struggled to translate museum experiences into design ideas, highlighting a need for closer facilitation.

Schedule and Structure

The CGJ followed a four-day arc:

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- **Day 1 (September 9, X11):** Game Making 101, group formation, role assignment via tarot cards.
- **Day 2 (September 10, NISV):** Exhibit exploration, design prompts, initial concept work.
- **Day 3 (September 12, X11):** Brainstorming with Crazy 8 exercise, prototyping, and feedback sessions.
- **Day 4 (September 13, X11):** Playtesting, peer feedback, expert jury evaluations, final pitches.

Participant Engagement

Students engaged with a variety of methods such as board game analysis, creative brainstorming, paper prototyping, and demonstrated enthusiasm during hands-on tasks. However, maintaining focus across a large cohort was challenging, with energy dips noted in museum sessions and longer brainstorming activities. Many students valued the feedback carousel on the final day, which provided a sense of validation and progress.

Research Methods

- Pre-surveys on gaming habits and expectations.
- Structured classroom and museum **observations** (4 researchers).
- **Vox pop interviews** in a dedicated space, conducted by students.
- Playtest and pitch video recordings.
- Itch.io devlogs documenting game design (though unevenly completed).

Documentation

Extensive documentation included daily photos, video recordings of playtests and pitches, and student-produced devlogs on Itch.io. Despite improvements from CGJ1, only six out of 15 games were properly published online, showing continued challenges in supporting consistent student documentation.

While only a portion of games were fully documented online, prototypes reflected student engagement with themes of democracy, equality, and media influence. Awards were given for categories like **Best Prototype**, **Most Culturally Rich**, and **Most Daring**, highlighting both creative ambition and cultural reflection.

4.6.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 15 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Hilversum CGJ2](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Hilversum CGJ2](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Differences & Equality Memory: A reflective memory game exploring the European value of equality, where players match cards depicting social differences and answer discussion prompts on discrimination and daily life, encouraging empathy and dialogue about inclusivity.

Evie's World: A single-player pixel game addressing the European value of equality, where players guide a girl rebuilding her life after a climate-induced forest fire, highlighting how environmental crises deepen social inequality and affect vulnerable groups most severely.

Table 13: Two example games from Hilversum CGJ2

Participant Feedback

Students expressed enjoyment of the hands-on prototyping and appreciated the expert feedback sessions, particularly those led by DROG on misinformation. These elements provided concrete learning moments and sparked meaningful discussions. However, many participants struggled with the intensity of the workload and the lack of clear communication beforehand. The host teacher had not adequately prepared either students or fellow teachers for the CGJ's demands, meaning that the disruption to the regular school week came as a surprise. For younger participants (under 18), the unclear expectations, absence of structured breaks, and limited buy-in to the broader purpose of the CGJ proved particularly challenging. As a result, some students lost interest partway through the process, with a few even becoming visibly frustrated. This highlighted how essential transparent communication, clear framing, and realistic expectations are for ensuring student engagement in future CGJs.

Figure 18, Welcome from the cultural facilitators to participants during Hilversum CGJ2.

Successes

- **Scale and reach** were significantly expanded, engaging 61 students and demonstrating the potential of embedding CGJs within formal education.
- **CGJ Kit improvements** through a consolidated handbook, role cards, and streamlined brainstorming reduced stress compared to the first CGJ.
- **Cross-sector cultural hub collaboration** was deepened, with CHI, CI, HEI, and school partners working closely alongside the Youth Advisory Board, strengthening the quadruple helix model.

Challenges

- **Cultural heritage integration** proved difficult, as many groups struggled to meaningfully connect museum visits and European values to their prototypes.
- **Participant focus** fluctuated, with some activities too long for younger attention spans, leading to dips in engagement.
- **Documentation gaps** persisted, as most teams did not complete full devlogs despite structured support, leaving an incomplete record of outcomes.

DBR Round 2 - Glocal Cultural Game Jams

05

5. DBR Round 2 – Glocal Cultural Game Jams

This section introduces the six glocal CGJs that formed the **second iteration of our Design-based Research process**. Building directly on the lessons of the initial six local CGJs, these events were designed not only to refine methods within each cultural hub but also to test how CGJs could operate and connect across a glocal context. The six local CGJs had already shown the potential of the format as a model for youth cultural participation, where creativity, heritage, and values could come together in playful and empowering ways. At the same time, they revealed several recurring challenges that needed to be addressed before the CGJs could be scaled or developed into glocal experiments.

5.0.1 Lessons Learned from DBR Round 1

Recruitment proved one of the main challenges. Open calls across cultural hubs often struggled to attract the desired mix of participants in terms of numbers, diversity, and preparation. In Hilversum, the first CGJ's open recruitment drew fewer participants than expected, while in Óbidos, reliance on university videogame students led to an underrepresentation of women. Later CGJs adopted more targeted strategies by embedding activities in schools and recruiting across complementary programmes to improve both participation levels and the balance of skills and perspectives.

Facilitation structure was another recurring tension. The first CGJs revealed how difficult it was to balance guidance with creative autonomy. In Hilversum, participants appreciated freedom but found too many brainstorming exercises overwhelming. Aarhus, by contrast, used a tightly scaffolded model that some felt constrained imagination. The main insight was the need for flexible facilitation: offering clear onramps for newcomers while preserving room for experimentation and self-direction.

Research and documentation also carried a heavy load. The previous CGJs required extensive surveys, ethical paperwork, and devlogs, which some participants found intrusive or time-consuming. Aarhus teams noted that reporting reduced prototyping time, while Óbidos participants felt over-surveyed. Later iterations streamlined these processes, embedding documentation directly into the CGJ. Tools like itch.io became not only research instruments but also creative showcases, making reflection a more integrated and meaningful part of the design process.

These lessons were formalised in **D3.2 Protocols 2**, which refined and extended the CGJ framework and Kit based on data and insights from the six local CGJs. The updated D3.2, Protocol 2 CGJ protocol articulated seven guiding CGJ principles (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025, pp. 37–39):

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- **CGJ Principle 1:** Three ways to run Cultural Game Jams
- **CGJ Principle 2:** Aimed at cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment
- **CGJ Principle 3:** Foster cultural curiosity and creativity
- **CGJ Principle 4:** Cultivate an “epic we” through Cultural Game Jams
- **CGJ Principle 5:** Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making
- **CGJ Principle 6:** Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation
- **CGJ Principle 7:** Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

These principles re-enforced the importance of co-creation, reflective practice, and value-sensitive game-making. They also emphasised empowered youth participation, stronger cross-sector collaboration, and facilitation strategies that balance cultural heritage and game-making guidance with participant creativity.

One of the key results of the updated CGJ protocols was the introduction of three **formats** of the CGJ Kit: Focused, Flexible, and Freeform (Nørgård and Holflod, 2025, p. 41). These formats frame CGJs as structured but adaptable processes for game-making as culture-making, offering organisers three levels of adjustability:

- **Focused** where all CGJ elements are determined at the project or organisational level –this also contains the minimum viable model for the CGJ Kit);
- **Flexible** where the QH Cultural Hub tailor the process to local needs; and
- **Freeform** where youth shape their own creative and collaborative journey based on the CGJ Kit.

Taken together, these formats allow CGJ organisers to determine whether a given intervention should prioritise consistency, local adaptation, or participant autonomy, depending on the aims and conditions of the cultural hub.

Most importantly, D3.2 Protocol 2 further integrated the CGJ Kit with the two foundational CGJ approaches: **Games through Culture**, which use cultural heritage as concrete game-making material, and **Games for Culture**, which address cultural or societal themes through the use of European values (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025). This distinction created two clear design pathways for the cultural hubs, ensuring that empowered participation could take the form of engaging tangible cultural heritage collections or engaging with civic cultural themes or issues through mixing tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

5.0.2 Glocal Approaches Incorporated in DBR Round 2

To give the six CGJs a more glocal character, WP4 led a co-creative and exploratory process involving partners from all three cultural hubs, including CHI, CI, HEI, and Youth Advisory Board (YAB) representatives. Together, these partners collaboratively defined and implemented strategies for meaningful cross-cultural hub collaboration. Through iterative

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dialogue and testing, this process resulted in three agreed-upon glocal elements that connected the CGJs across Europe while preserving local specificity.

First, to create more **(a)synchronous communication** between cultural hubs and their participants, a Discord server was created with a multitude of channels to keep topics organised. Since these CGJs were always organised during different weeks, video exchanges of greetings between cultural hubs were also organised so participants could better feel part of a shared European experiment rather than an activity for class.

Secondly, the **Youth Advisory Boards (YABs)** gained a stronger role in shaping not just the content of the CGJs but also the greater project. YAB members created their own communication channels to communicate across cultural hubs and feed input to a project-level Advisory Board. These measures gave young people more influence not only in their own CGJs but also in shaping the overall direction of EPIC-WE.

Third, the six glocal CGJs in the second round of DBR were strategically designed to test the- *Games for Culture CGJ Kit* and the *Games through Culture CGJ Kit*. The cultural hubs collaborated to create a shared **umbrella theme implemented across the three cultural hubs** ensuring collaboration across all CGJs while still allowing space for local cultural hubs to adapt the themes to their own cultural heritage contexts, sites, and collections.

5.0.3 Third Iteration of CGJs: That's Not Fair!

The third iteration of CGJs followed the *Games for Culture CGJ Kit*, which positioned game-making as a heritage- and value-sensitive civic act. The shared theme *That's Not Fair!* invited youth to design games focusing on fairness, (in)justice, and inclusion/exclusion in society and everyday life. Building on the CGJ Kit's methods and tools for value-sensitive and culture-sensitive design, participants explored how rules, systems, narratives, and relationships shape what feels "fair" or "unfair," and translated these insights into game mechanics, narratives, gameworlds, and playful interactions. Expert Councils and Youth Advisory Boards supported reflection, linking personal experiences to broader civic and social concerns.

- **Aarhus CGJ3 (March 3–7, 2025):** Ran as a five-day, multi-venue CGJ across ARoS, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University; students made value-sensitive games for culture about fairness, inclusion, and justice inspired by the cultural heritage collection.
- **Óbidos CGJ3 (February 4–7, 2025):** Mixed secondary school and university participants co-created games for culture on *That's Not Fair!*, linking the cultural heritage events of December 1st 1973 (Reunion of the Captains) and the Portuguese April 25th Carnation Revolution to questions of democracy and justice.

- **Hilversum CGJ3 (February 17–28, 2025):** Two-week format embedded in AUAS tackled media fairness and European values using the NISV cultural heritage digital archive and depot as inspiration.

5.0.4 Fourth Iteration of CGJ: Heritage Remixed

The final iteration of CGJs were guided by the *Games through Culture CGJ Kit*, which encouraged participants to engage the tangible cultural heritage collections, artefacts, sites, and traditions as concrete game-making material. The shared theme Heritage Remixed challenged youth to reinterpret, remix, or reconfigure tangible cultural heritage in playful and innovative ways, connecting past and present while imagining new cultural heritage futures. Rather than treating tangible cultural heritage as static decoration or dead history, participants used it to shape living interactions and experiences in the form of game mechanics, narratives, worlds, and aesthetics, creating games through culture that invited players of these games to experience cultural heritage as interactive, living, and participatory.

- **Aarhus CGJ4 (March 21–May 9, 2025):** A six-week “slow jam” where Digital Design and Computer Science students remixed ARoS public-domain cultural heritage artworks into games through culture in the form of AR/VR prototypes.
- **Óbidos CGJ4 (May 13–16, 2025):** Four-day CGJ (with a pre-CGJ cultural heritage activity) where mixed-age teams reinterpreted local folklore and heritage into games through culture.
- **Hilversum CGJ4 (September 10–16, 2025):** Multi-location CGJ with university students focused on past and future relationship with water in the Netherlands using archival cultural heritage materials in their making of games through culture.

In the next sections, you will find the six detailed case studies from the glocal CGJs using the same template as the first round of CGJ cases.

5.1 Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ3 (Winter 2025)

Figure 19, Participants showcasing their game prototype during Aarhus CGJ3.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: March 3–7, 2025

Location: ARoS, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University in Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 5 days across one week

Participants: 45 first-year Digital Design students (ages 20-32) from Aarhus University

Number of Games: 11 prototypes

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture)

Table 14: Overview of Aarhus CGJ3

5.1.1 Introduction

The third Aarhus CGJ took place on March 3–7, 2025, as the ninth edition of the EPIC-WE project. This week-long event brought together 45 first-year Digital Design students from Aarhus University for an intensive creative process that combined cultural exploration, contemporary art, and societal reflection.

This CGJ was set across three venues: ARoS Aarhus Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University. The CGJ created diverse and inspiring environments for play, design, and reflection. Guided by the **glocal theme** *That's Not Fair!*, participants explored fairness and

inequality as fundamental forces shaping society. The CGJ Brief encouraged students to address issues such as economic disparity, social inclusion, and climate justice. The goal was to design value-sensitive cultural games (*games for culture*) that provoke playful, critical, and empathetic conversations about what fairness means to youth in Europe today.

5.1.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Aarhus University (AU):** Led planning, research, and coordination.
- **ARoS Aarhus Art Museum (ARoS):** Provided curatorial input, managed logistics, and hosted activities in the museum space.
- **Filmby Aarhus (AAKS):** Oversaw recruitment, documentation, and digital platforms (Itch.io and Discord).
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Advised on recruitment and facilitation design, and provided youth perspectives throughout planning and reflection.
- **Industry Partners:** Mothworks, Funday Games, and Chop Chop Games provided inspiration talks, mentorship, and feedback as part of the Expert Council.

5.1.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation for the third Aarhus CGJ built directly on lessons from earlier events, while introducing several new methods to improve alignment, participation, and facilitation. Short, sprint-like planning meetings between Aarhus University, ARoS, and Filmby Aarhus clarified roles and coordinated logistics across three venues. A more deliberate integration with the Digital Design curriculum ensured the CGJ was embedded in teaching schedules, making participation feasible and academically relevant for first-year students.

Recruitment shifted from open calls to a closed, programme-based model. By embedding the CGJ directly into the BA Digital Design curriculum, organisers secured 45 committed participants with a shared baseline of knowledge and expectations. This approach ensured both high participation numbers and clearer links between CGJ activities, coursework, and academic progression.

Facilitation methods were refined in response to challenges from previous CGJs. A **focused CGJ Kit** was used to structure the week, reducing cognitive overload while still supporting cultural-creative exploration. In addition, three additional innovations were tested in the planning of this CGJ. A new mini-council session was also introduced midweek, giving participants earlier feedback from experts before the main Expert Council. This helped students adjust their cultural heritage game concepts at an earlier stage, rather than late in development. Another innovation was the introduction of the P5 Play game engine, chosen collaboratively for its accessibility, JavaScript-based design, and curricular fit. While this created a steep learning curve, it also standardised the technical foundation across all CGJ teams and connected directly to students' coursework. Finally, youth involvement in

planning was strengthened through including the YAB.. A dedicated youth liaison hired by the AU team ensured that youth perspectives shaped preparatory decisions and facilitation approaches, providing deeper youth engagement than in earlier CGJs.

Figure 20, Updated Ideation Wheel and CGJ Brief from Aarhus CGJ3.

5.1.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections:

The CGJ foregrounded installation art from ARoS's contemporary collection, encouraging students to reimagine artworks and cultural heritage narratives as interactive experiences. By combining art, European values, and civic reflection, participants explored how fairness and (in)justice play out in cultural and social systems.

Schedule & Structure:

- **Day 1 (March 3, ARoS):** Introduction to CGJs, Experience phase artwalk at ARoS, and a workshop on cultural heritage and game culture with Stanisław Krawczyk.
- **Day 2 (March 4, ARoS):** Play phase with ideation and mini-council feedback.
- **Day 3 (March 5, Filmbj Aarhus):** Company visits to Funday Games and Chop Chop Games, followed by the Imagine phase and Expert Council feedback.
- **Day 4 (March 6, AU):** Create phase – full-day games for culture prototyping.
- **Day 5 (March 7, ARoS):** Final development, submission of prototypes and logs, and the EXPO of games for culture at ARoS.

Participant Empowered Participation:

Students demonstrated high agency throughout the week, independently selecting and interpreting cultural heritage themes and values. The Focused CGJ Kit supported this autonomy while ensuring scaffolding was available when needed. During the Games EXPO, most CGJ teams complemented their games for culture with installation-inspired paratexts, enriching their cultural heritage presentation and engaging the museum audience.

Research Methods:

- Pre- and post-surveys
- Vox pop interviews
- Participatory observation and field notes
- Visual ethnography
- Research through design
- Documentation of prototypes and game logs on Itch.io

Documentation:

All 11 prototypes were uploaded to Itch.io with detailed logs. Professional photographers from ARoS/AAKS captured the process, supplemented by student and researcher documentation. Coverage was shared through AU, ARoS, and Filmby platforms, including news articles and online showcases.

5.1.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 11 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Aarhus CGJ3](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Aarhus CGJ3](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Your Filtered Life: A role-playing game where randomness and starting conditions determine opportunities, reflecting on equality, freedom, and how personal circumstances shape life paths.

Know Your Neighbour(?): A puzzle game set in a Danish apartment, asking players to identify five items that don't belong. It uses humour and observation to provoke reflection on prejudice, cultural norms, and inclusion.

Table 15: Two example games from Aarhus CGJ3

Participant Feedback

Students described the CGJ as engaging, enjoyable, and valuable, combining cultural heritage exploration with hands-on game design. Many highlighted that the integration of cultural heritage, contemporary art, and societal values and themes challenged them to think critically while also strengthening collaboration and creative problem-solving. The opportunity to work with external professionals, cultural facilitators, and industry mentors was especially valued, as it provided career insights and tangible connections to the wider game and cultural sectors.

At the same time, participants noted several challenges in pacing and structure. The first day felt overloaded with lectures and conceptual input, which left less room for hands-on experimentation. Conversely, the final days felt rushed, with teams calling for more dedicated development time earlier in the week. Game logs, though appreciated as a reflective tool, were described as “confusing and administratively heavy,” with some students unclear on expectations or struggling to keep up with the deliverables alongside prototyping.

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Despite these challenges, many students reported significant learning outcomes. They connected practical design skills with analytical reflection, gaining experience in project management, teamwork, and translating cultural or societal issues into interactive designs. Several reflected on how the CGJ allowed them to “move from confusion to empowered participation,” growing more confident in their ability to critically engage with fairness, values, and cultural heritage through game-making.

The Games for Culture EXPO at ARoS concluded the week on a high note, with participants proud of their games and appreciative of the chance to present them in a professional cultural heritage space. The EXPO not only celebrated their created games for culture but also demonstrated the potential of CGJs as learning environments that blend creativity, cultural heritage, civic reflection, and game-making as a format for cultural innovation.

Figure 21, EXPO during Aarhus CGJ3.

Successes

- **Integration of cultural heritage and values** was achieved, as participants successfully embedded the theme of fairness with societal and cultural challenges, European values, and tangible cultural heritage from ARoS into their games for culture prototypes, supported by detailed game logs documenting their design process.
- **Learning outcomes** were strengthened, with students connecting practical skills in game-making to analytical reflection, thereby developing both creative and academic competencies.
- **Youth empowerment** was clearly demonstrated, as participants grew more confident and critical in their engagement with cultural heritage and civic issues,

showing intrinsic motivation through the game-making as culture-making process.

Challenges

- **Digital infrastructure** created barriers, as platforms for communication and documentation were fragmented, highlighting the need to prioritise one or two central tools in future CGJs.
- **Game logs and documentation** were overly complex, and simplified formats would better support student workflow and improve communicative value.
- **Facilitation clarity** was lacking, as the absence of a single named lead facilitator sometimes caused confusion, underlining the importance of clearer leadership roles.

5.2 Óbidos Cultural Hub CGJ3 (Winter 2025)

Figure 22, Final pitches from Óbidos CGJ3.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: February 4–7, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 38 youth (19 students from LU, 19 secondary school students)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (1 physical game + 8 digital games)

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture), Linking the theme to the December 1st “Reunion of the Captains” in Óbidos to the Portuguese April 25th Carnation Revolution

Table 16: Overview of Óbidos CGJ3

5.2.1 Introduction

The third Óbidos CGJ took place on February 4–7, 2025, marking the cultural hub’s contribution to the global “That’s Not Fair!” theme. Over four days, 38 youth participants designed nine prototypes inspired by Portugal’s democratic history, linking the clandestine 1973 “Reunion of the Captains” in Óbidos with the 1974 April 25th Carnation Revolution.

The CGJ balanced cultural exploration with creative game-making, encouraging participants to reflect on values of freedom, justice, and democracy in playful, critical ways.

5.2.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Municipality of Óbidos (CMO):** Provided the venue, managed accommodation, meals, and materials, led theme selection and lecture, organised guided tours; one main facilitator on site; visit from Mayor Filipe Daniel;
- **Lusófona University (LU):** Designed the CGJ structure, prepared materials, adapted research instruments, recruited participants, ran ideation workshops, and collected data; 4 researchers and 2 facilitators;
- **Battlesheep (BS):** Supported logistics and facilitation throughout the CGJ.
- **External Contributors:** Professors Hugo Barata and Inês Marques (ideation and group dynamics), cultural facilitators, and art curators;
- **Youth Participants:** 19 Lusófona University students (video games, visual arts, sound design), 19 secondary school students. YAB members attended as observers/participants, gaining first-hand CGJ experience for future facilitation roles.

5.2.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation focused on aligning the CGJ's theme with the municipality's cultural vision and the EPIC-WE glocal framework. While the cultural hub did not formally integrate the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit due to time constraints, Lusófona designed a set of ideation activities, including Twine storytelling workshops, group dynamics, and a shadow projection exercise using natural materials, that framed the pre-CGJ day. These methods aimed to spark creativity but proved uneven: Lusófona students engaged enthusiastically, while high school participants were less responsive, highlighting the need for more integrated mixed-group activities.

Recruitment drew on Lusófona's video games course's Discord server and outreached to visual arts and sound design students too, yielding 19 university participants. Another 19 high school students were recruited via their teachers, though this teacher-driven process left some participants feeling less ownership of their involvement. Logistically, Lusófona managed equipment, Discord, and Itch.io, while CMO arranged accommodation in municipal houses and set up the Creativity Square as the CGJ venue.

Figure 23, Tour of the City of Óbidos during Óbidos CGJ3.

5.2.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The theme *That's Not Fair!* was framed through Portugal's democratic history, linking the clandestine "Reunion of the Captains" in Óbidos (December 1, 1973) with the April 25th Carnation Revolution (1974). A lecture and guided visit contextualised the cultural heritage theme, highlighting democracy, justice, and freedom as central European values. While participants integrated the April 25th theme prominently into their games, connections to the Captains' meeting were less evident in most games. This revealed the need for more focused scaffolding to help youth bridge complex historical events with contemporary concerns.

Schedule and Structure

The CGJ followed a four-day arc:

- **Day 1 (February 4):** Pre-CGJ activities such as arrival and accommodation, Twine workshop for high school students, cultural visit in Óbidos village, group dynamics led by Hugo Barata, shadow projection ideation by Inês Marques, and team formation;
- **Day 2 (February 5):** Development starts, autonomous team work, creation of Itch.io game logs, and idea presentations;

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- **Day 3 (February 6):** Development continuation, ongoing development with a mid-point checkpoint, where teams uploaded screenshots and shared progress;
- **Day 4 (February 7):** Final submissions, public showcase with invited guests (including the Mayor of Óbidos and Captain Octávio Pinto), followed by a post-mortem reflection session.

Participant Engagement

University students, particularly from visual arts and sound design courses, integrated well into teams and contributed strongly to creative outputs. Secondary school participants were less consistently engaged, showing limited interest during the city visit and ideation exercises. While participants had autonomy in team formation and project direction, they were not involved in theme selection. Future editions could improve collaboration across age groups through structured mixed-team activities.

Research Methods

- Pre-survey (demographics, gameplay/creation habits, cultural heritage, European values, games' impact) via Microsoft Forms;
- Post-survey (experience, logistics, outcomes) delivered through Discord on the final day;
- Game Analysis survey (Likert scale 1–7, researcher reflections);
- Observations of engagement, teamwork, and group dynamics by facilitators and researchers;
- Post-mortem session discussions with LU students.

Documentation

Documentation included photos shared on EPIC-WE social media, interviews with participants and facilitators, and event notes for project history. Games were uploaded to Itch.io with descriptions, screenshots, and gameplay videos. Despite these efforts, engagement with documentation was uneven between groups.

5.2.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 9 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Óbidos CGJ3](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Óbidos CGJ3](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Blue Brigade: A satirical game where players act as PIDE censors armed with a giant blue pencil, forced to follow arbitrary daily rules. Its stylised setting and ironic tone highlighted democracy, resistance, and the inevitability of liberation.

Bufo Catcher: A replayable deduction game where players act as guards at a secret junta meeting, tasked with exposing a traitor by spotting inconsistencies in names, ranks, and passwords. The design captured the paranoia of dictatorship through tense puzzle mechanics.

Table 17: Two example games from Óbidos CGJ3

Participant Feedback

Most participants reported a positive experience, with 61% stating the CGJ met expectations and 36% saying it exceeded them. High school students described the event as “challenging but fun,” while Lusófona participants emphasised collaboration and creativity: “It went beyond my expectations in terms of teamwork and imagination.” However, some struggled to connect the theme to their designs, with nearly half responding “I don’t know” when asked if their perception of fairness had changed. Logistical feedback was mixed: while meals and the showcase were praised, accommodation and communication were cited as weaker aspects.

Figure 24, Group photo from Óbidos CGJ3.

Successes

- **Cross-disciplinary cultural heritage creativity** strengthened games for culture prototypes, with sound design and visual arts students adding artistic polish and depth;
- **YAB empowered participation** offered members valuable first-hand experience of the CGJ, preparing them for more active roles in facilitation and planning;
- **Embedding democracy and resistance** in game narratives demonstrated the ability of CGJs to engage youth with civic cultural heritage values through game-making.

Challenges

- **Limited collaboration between groups** was observed, as university and secondary school students often worked in separate clusters, requiring more structured activities to bridge the divide;
- **Pre-CGJ timing** reduced reflection, as cultural visits and ideation occurred too close to the start of development; holding them earlier could have deepened integration;
- **Variable engagement among high school students** was noted, particularly during longer cultural tasks, suggesting the need for shorter, more interactive activities.

5.3 Hilversum Cultural Hub CGJ3 (Winter 2025)

Figure 25, Participants building their game prototypes for Hilversum CGJ3.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: February 17–28, 2025

Location: Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), Amsterdam, Netherlands and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 2 weeks (pre-CGJ activities and a 1 week CGJ)

Participants: 23 students from the Creative Research Methods minor (AUAS)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (8 team games plus 1 solo game after a team split)

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture)

Table 18: Overview of Hilversum CGJ3

5.3.1 Introduction

Hilversum's third CGJ ran across two weeks, combining a museum-led inspiration track with a focused production week at AUAS. Students first explored Sound & Vision's Media Museum and archive, then returned to AUAS to design and prototype board and card games that examined fairness and media culture through the lens of European values. The

cohort produced nine playable prototypes and documented their process and outcomes on itch.io, supported by a structured schedule, expert feedback, and templated devlogs.

5.3.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV):** Cultural hub management, production leadership, cultural collection integration, communications, and tours of the depot. External to the cultural hub team, museum hosts, online collection staff supported participants learning more about the collection.
- **Dropstuff Media (DM):** Designed and facilitated the game-making process and core methods.
- **Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS):** Led research before, during, and after the CGJ, and facilitated itch.io documentation; teachers from the minor booked rooms and connected CGJ outputs to minor learning goals.
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Participated in preparation meetings, informed programme tweaks such as adding guided museum prompts, and assisted with observations and testimonials.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Three expert lecturers in gaming from AUAS external to the project provided mid-week feedback for the expert council. The final jury included an independent game designer and experts from Control Magazine and EIT Culture & Creativity.

5.3.3 Planning and Preparation

Building on CGJ2, partners ran structured design sprints, assigning tasks to named individuals rather than sub-teams to increase accountability. An intern helped develop the new Archive Memory Game, and school collaboration simplified logistics such as room bookings. The team noted that earlier timelines and at least two core producers plus an intern would prevent deadline crunch. YAB members joined full-team prep sessions and separate check-ins, shaping the level of guidance during the museum day.

The CGJ was embedded as a one-week project in AUAS's Creative Research Methods minor, yielding a committed cohort of 23. This closed **recruitment** streamlined expectations but reduced disciplinary diversity compared to open calls.

Figure 26, Game-making materials for prototyping during Hilversum CGJ3.

5.3.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

Students worked within the glocal theme *That's Not Fair!* and engaged with Sound & Vision's collection through three touchpoints: a guided museum visit using a tailored booklet, a behind-the-scenes depot tour with curators, and a bespoke **Archive Memory Game** that paired historical fragments on topics like censorship and wage gaps across eras. Partners later observed that values and collection prompts remained broad for some teams, recommending tighter scoping in future, for example assigning specific European values per group and surfacing more game-relevant collection examples.

Schedule and Structure

The CGJ followed the EPIC-WE flow over two weeks, using the first week to get to know the collection, the theme, and the principles of game design. In the second week, the participants focused on going through the four phases of the EPIC process, producing their games:

Week 1 (Pre-CGJ Activities)

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- **Pre- CGJ Activities:** Game Design 101 kick-off session at AUAS with group formation, Discord onboarding, surveys, and an introductory Game Design 101 workshop to level the playing field (February 17, AUAS). Visit to the Sound & Vision archive including depot tour, museum exploration, and Archive Memory Game to connect students with cultural materials and European values (February 19, NISV).

Week 2

- **Day 1 (February 24, AUAS):** Start of the CGJ Experience phase with brainstorming, concept drafting, paper prototyping, and first itch.io devlogs.
- **Day 2 (February 25, AUAS):** Continued prototyping, peer playtesting, feedback sessions, and documentation updates via itch.io.
- **Day 3 (February 26, AUAS):** Prototyping refinements with the Expert Council, Vox pop interviews, and iterative feedback, followed by devlog updates.
- **Day 4 (February 28, AUAS):** Final devlogs, prototype polish, public pitches in market-style format, jury evaluations, awards ceremony, and closing reception.

Post-CGJ Activities: a group of four students from the Creative Research Minor continued their game development and conducted their own creative research project, *Perceptions of Play – Can You See the Value?* in the second half of the semester.

Participant Engagement

Since students already worked together within the minor, organisers reduced icebreakers and focused on design practice. Teams exercised agency within the theme, choosing which fairness questions and European values to address. Many games explored unequal starting points and systemic (dis)advantages. The cultural link tended to reflect museum modes of display rather than the deeper archive content, which partners plan to address by weighting the depot tour more and sharpening prompts.

Research Methods

Pre-CGJ surveys on background and habits, paired-observer field notes using a shared grid, YAB-assisted observations, vox-pop interviews in a quiet room with printed prompts, recorded pitch videos, three templated devlogs per team on itch.io, and a post-CGJ survey administered via teachers. Organisers noted research framing should happen earlier in future to improve participant understanding.

Documentation

Itch.io pages were pre-created with devlog templates. Log-in and two-factor authentication caused minor access issues, prompting a future switch to letting teams use personal accounts and granting admin access. Discord operated as the main information channel,

though it was mostly one-way and needed streamlining. A communications officer covered key moments for post-event stories; photography was continuous but constrained by consent, which suggests a lighter-footprint approach next time. An award for Best Documented Game incentivised fuller pages.

5.3.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 9 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Hilversum CGJ3](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Hilversum CGJ3](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

Viral Spiral: A decision-making board game where influencers choose to share, report, or ignore news items while a game master mediates outcomes. Players learn to question sources and experience how virality and follower counts reward or punish their choices, opening discussion about the tension between press freedom and misinformation.

De Buren: A neighbour-help game about elderly loneliness, where players visit residents, select activities, and escort them safely home. The design raises awareness of social isolation and encourages small, caring actions, even though the collection link would benefit from deeper integration.

Table 19: Two example games from Hilversum CG3

Participant Feedback

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Students described the CGJ as a valuable, hands-on introduction to cultural heritage game design that balanced creativity with reflection. Many highlighted how the mix of fast prototyping and real-world cultural input from the NISV depot helped them see how abstract ideas like fairness and justice could be expressed as playable systems. The Cultural Input Day was widely appreciated for grounding the theme “That’s Not Fair” in tangible heritage, although several students suggested tighter links between the archival materials and their final game briefs. Peer-to-peer playtesting was seen as both motivating and challenging. Participants valued the feedback but wished for more time to test within their own groups before presenting to others. For many first-time gamemakers, the Game Design 101 session proved essential for building confidence and establishing a shared vocabulary. Beginners particularly valued the structured approach to ideation and prototyping, while more experienced students expressed a desire for deeper technical exploration or advanced facilitation.

A few participants commented on organisational aspects, especially around Discord communication and channel navigation. The digital workspace felt “too busy” for some, making it hard to track key announcements or file locations. Overall, participants left feeling that the CGJ was intense but rewarding.

Several teams from the Creative Research Methods minor indicated they would like to continue developing their prototypes beyond the event. One group extended their concept into a larger creative research project titled *Perceptions of Play – Can You See the Value?*, which examined how game settings shape players’ interpretations and how shifting context alters meaning. This illustrated how CGJ participation can spark longer-term creative inquiry and sustained cultural game-making.

Figure 27, Cultural facilitator giving a tour of the NISV archive during Hilversum CGJ3.

Successes

- Embedding the CGJ in the AUAS minor provided **scale within education**, securing a committed cohort and predictable scheduling that boosted delivery quality.
- The **purposeful cultural heritage touchpoints** of the Archive Memory Game and depot tour made the collection more tangible and reusable as teaching assets for future CGJs.
- **Process visibility** was improved through pre-built itch.io pages and templated devlogs, which supported consistent documentation and made the design journey easier to review and assess.

Challenges

- The **cultural heritage integration depth** was limited, as many games reflected museum display modes more than specific archive materials, suggesting the need for tighter prompts and value assignments.
- **Facilitation capacity** was stretched, with one main facilitator proving insufficient for a two-week arc; at least two core facilitators plus a back-up are recommended.
- The CGJ **channels and communication** setup created friction, with cluttered Discord channels, one-way exchanges, and 2FA complicating early itch.io access; a leaner channel strategy and simpler account workflow will reduce these issues.

5.4 Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ4 (Spring 2025)

Figure 28, Participants playtesting in Aarhus CGJ4.

Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, May 2025. Used with permission.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)

Date: March 21 – May 9, 2025

Location: ARoS Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University, Denmark

Duration: 6 weeks (slow jam across alternating sessions)

Participants: 61 students, age 22-28 (24 Digital Design, 37 Computer Science, Aarhus University)

Number of Games: 18 prototypes

Theme: *Heritage Remixed* (Games through Culture), using VR/AR technologies

Table 20: Overview of Aarhus CGJ4

5.4.1 Introduction

The fourth Aarhus CGJ, held between March and May 2025, marked the final iteration of the EPIC-WE CGJ series. Designed as a slow jam spanning six weeks, the event linked **ARoS Art Museum, Aarhus University (AU), and Filmby Aarhus** through a sequence of structured sessions grounded in the glocal theme “*Heritage Remixed.*”

ARoS's Human Nature collection was selected as the creative foundation for the CGJ, offering public-domain artworks with strong narrative potential, including romanticised landscapes, social scenes, and symbolic objects that inspired themes such as propaganda, consumerism, and cultural revisionism. Participants explored how public-domain artworks at ARoS could be reimagined as playable cultural heritage experiences that link tangible heritage with European values and contemporary issues such as consumerism, freedom, and belonging. The format emphasised games through culture, positioning creative reinterpretation as a form of cultural participation where tangible heritage becomes concrete game-making material.

Building on earlier iterations, this CGJ introduced an extended focus on XR technologies, encouraging participants to use augmented and virtual reality as tools for cultural expression. The CGJ ultimately resulted in 18 different AR and VR games through culture, all developed in Unity. These prototypes showcased the creative potential of immersive media, ranging from VR explorations of propaganda to playful AR interventions that reimagined artworks and museum spaces as interactive cultural worlds.

5.4.2 Partners / People Involved

- **ARoS Art Museum (ARoS):** Curated artworks, designed artwalks, hosted Games through Culture EXPO.
- **Aarhus University (AU):** Led pedagogical design, facilitation, and research documentation.
- **Filmy Aarhus (AAKS):** Coordinated communications, technical setup (Itch.io, Discord), and event logistics.
- **MANND / Mothworks (External CIs):** Provided XR inspiration and workshops for Unity development.
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Supported facilitation and inclusion, focusing on peer engagement.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Amalie Kjær from Mothworks, ARoS' project Manager Kasper Marius Nørmark, Claus Toft-Nielsen from Aarhus University and one of the youth participants from the very first CGJ in EPIC-WE representing youth.

5.4.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation for the slow jam built directly on lessons from the previous Aarhus CGJ events. Partners from ARoS, AU, and Filmy Aarhus held sprint-style meetings to define responsibilities, synchronise schedules, and plan the flow between venues. The CGJ was fully embedded in the **Digital Design and Computer Science curricula** (5–10 ECTS, pass/fail), ensuring consistent participation but producing a mix of intrinsic and course-driven motivation.

ARoS selected and curated artworks from the *Human Nature* exhibition, designing guided artwalks that introduced embodied methods to tangible cultural heritage such as “Step into the painting” to help students connect with artistic and historical context. AU structured the CGJ around the CGJ Fixed Kit while Filmby Aarhus supported communication, technical coordination, and EXPO logistics.

Industry partners MANND and Mothworks provided technical input and inspiration on XR design. The inclusion of the YAB helped ensure the facilitation reflected youth perspectives on access, community, and creative inclusion.

Figure 29, Expo stand in Aarhus CGJ4.

Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, May 2025. Used with permission.

5.4.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The CGJ used ARoS’s *Human Nature* collection as a foundation for creating games through using cultural heritage as tangible game-making material for new ways of interacting with and experiencing cultural heritage. Students examined how art at ARoS could come alive or how romanticised depictions of nature and society in the artworks could be “remixed” into new narratives addressing propaganda, consumption, and social justice. A facilitation prompt of “Step into the painting. Where do you land? ... Who dares to share?” further supported this process, encouraging participants to explore the hidden narratives within the artworks. European values were woven into gameplay: freedom through mechanics and

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storytelling, democracy and dignity through player interactions, and equality and human rights through aesthetic choices and moral decision-making. The artwalk proved a key cultural-creative spark, helping students translate static cultural heritage artworks into playable cultural game worlds that empowered players with both cultural critique and imagination.

Schedule and Structure

The Aarhus CGJ followed a six-week arc of alternating one-day weekly sessions across AU, Filmby Aarhus, and ARoS:

- **Day 1 (March 21, ARoS):** Kick-off of the CGJ with embodied art walk and introductions to the CGJ Kit, guided by ARoS art educators.
- **Day 2 (March 28, AU):** Inspiration talks from MANND and Mothworks, followed by early concept and ideation sessions.
- **Day 3 (April 4, AU):** Expert Council feedback on scope and concept clarity, encouraging participants to refine ideas into feasible prototypes.
- **Day 4 (April 11, AU):** Combined Imagine + Create session with early prototyping and playtesting supported by technical mentors.
- **Day 5 (May 2, AU):** Final build and documentation sprint, focusing on completing Unity prototypes, refining visuals, and preparing Itch.io submissions.
- **Day 6 (May 9, ARoS):** Public Games Through Culture EXPO showcasing 18 XR and AR prototypes created during the CGJ.

Participant Engagement

Engagement peaked during embodied and social phases, especially the artwalk, Expert Council, and EXPO showcase because students experienced direct ownership of their ideas. Motivation dipped in more lecture-style sessions and when technical issues with XR tools disrupted progress, particularly for Computer Science teams.

Despite these hurdles, students demonstrated strong collaborative learning and cultural heritage reflection. Digital Design participants led on concept development and cultural heritage framing, while Computer Science students contributed technical realisation, resulting in hybrid outcomes that fused creative and analytical strengths.

Research Methods

- Participatory observation and reflective field notes
- Vox-pop interviews with participants
- Visual ethnography (photos, videos, process documentation)
- Research through design analysis of prototypes

Documentation

All 18 prototypes were uploaded to Itch.io and supported with images, videos, and

reflective devlogs. Documentation was handled collaboratively by AU researchers and AAKS photographers.

5.4.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 18 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Aarhus CGJ4](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Aarhus CGJ4](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

ReStory: A 360° puzzle-adventure inspired by Vilhelm Kyhn's *View over Vejle Fjord*, where players traverse a fragmented landscape shaped by human impact. The game highlights how consumption alters both culture and environment.

Museum of Dreams: A surreal VR exploration where players shrink to child size to remix European artworks in a sandbox of colour, sound, and imagination. The experience transforms heritage into participatory play.

Table 21: Two example games from Aarhus CGJ4

Participant Feedback

Students described the slow jam as a rich but demanding process that blended art, technology, and social reflection. Many praised the **art walk** and **Expert Council** for grounding creativity in cultural context and providing tangible feedback. Participants appreciated the longer structure for reflection but found XR tools unstable and collaboration uneven across disciplines.

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Some participants mentioned challenges balancing coursework and CGJ tasks, noting that while the hybrid format increased depth, it required clearer communication about expectations and deliverables. Despite this, the final EXPO created strong ownership and celebration, positioning the students as cultural co-creators within a professional museum environment.

Figure 30, Participants taking a tour of ARoS in Aarhus CGJ4.
Note. Photograph by Mads Smidstrup, March 2025. Used with permission.

Successes

- **Structured CGJ Kit phases** provided a clear workflow, helping teams balance creativity and deliverables.
- **Cultural heritage anchoring** through the Human Nature collection inspired original, imaginative, and cultural-critical reinterpretations of heritage.
- **Cross-disciplinary learning** between design and programming students produced innovative XR prototypes.

Challenges

- **Technical fragility** of XR setups caused frustration and hindered final testing.
- **Motivational gaps** emerged between intrinsically and course-driven participants.
- **Communication clarity** on Discord and between classes needed improvement to avoid confusion.

5.5 Óbidos Cultural Hub CGJ4 (Spring 2025)

Figure 31, Pre-CGJ activity during Óbidos CGJ4.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)

Date: May 13–16, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 41 total (20 from Escola Secundária Josefa de Óbidos; 21 from Lusófona University)

Number of Games: 10 prototypes (one made by a teacher)

Theme: *Heritage Remixed* (Games through Culture), focus on local folklore heritage

Table 22: Overview of Óbidos CGJ4

5.5.1 Introduction

The fourth Óbidos CGJ, held on May 13–16, 2025, invited secondary school and university students to reinterpret local folklore and cultural traditions through game design. Hosted again in the medieval town of Óbidos, the jam combined artistic exploration with

collaborative learning, encouraging participants to remix heritage narratives into playable forms. The event followed the EPIC-WE framework, with an emphasis on *freedom* as the guiding European value. Participants transformed myths, local legends, and cultural imagery into interactive experiences that reflected contemporary issues of identity, belonging, and creativity.

5.5.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Municipality of Óbidos (CMO):** Provided organisational and logistical support, including venue setup and accommodation; two representatives from the Centro de Design de Interiores contributed to cultural facilitation.
- **Lusófona University (LU):** Three professors led facilitation, mentorship, and research data collection; managed equipment, online platforms, and surveys.
- **Battlesheep (BS):** One professional representative contributed to feedback sessions and mentoring.
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Two members joined as assistants and observers, gaining experience to support future facilitation roles.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Game-making experts from UL and BS and cultural experts from CMO.

5.5.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation involved close coordination between the Municipality of Óbidos, Lusófona University, Battlesheep, and local cultural partners. Tasks included designing the agenda, selecting the theme, recruiting participants, and curating cultural reference materials for the Ideation Wheel and Game Logs. The theme “Cultural Heritage Remix” with a focus on folklore and oral history was selected collaboratively between the Youth Advisory Board and Óbidos’ cultural leadership, ensuring alignment with both local identity and EPIC-WE project values.

Recruitment at LU was conducted via course channels and a Google Form, ensuring diversity across gender, skill level, and experience. Secondary school students were recruited as a full class to ensure inclusion and equality.

A key highlight was the **pre-CGJ cultural visit**, held one week before the event, which included a guided village tour of Óbidos’ folklore sites. This gave participants time to reflect on the legends and begin shaping concepts before entering the intensive CGJ phase.

Figure 32, Cultural Facilitators helping youth during Óbidos CGJ4.

5.5.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The CGJ aimed to integrate the European value of *freedom* through reinterpretations of Óbidos' folklore and local legends. While students engaged creatively with the idea of heritage, the direct connection to European values and narrative depth varied. Some games reimagined local myths symbolically, while others leaned more on historical or aesthetic cues. Facilitators later noted the need for tighter alignment between heritage sources, values, and gameplay structure.

Schedule and Structure

The Óbidos CGJ followed the EPIC-WE phases of Inspiration, Ideation, Creation, and Reflection, supported by Game Logs and guided facilitation:

- **Day 1 (May 13)** Pre-CGJ activities with arrival in Óbidos, check-in, guided folklore tour, and introductions to local legends and the CGJ theme.
- **Day 2 (May 14):** Team-building exercises, interdisciplinary grouping, brainstorming, and *Game Log 1: Experience* reflection.
- **Day 3 (May 15):** Game development, mid-point pitches, and *Game Logs 3–4 (Imagine/Create)*; submission of Itch.io entries.

- **Day 4 (May 16):** Final polishing, reflections, and public showcase at the Creativity Square, followed by departures.

Participant Engagement

Engagement remained high during team-building and early design sessions. The pre-CGJ visit enriched cultural understanding and encouraged creativity. However, the timing of the Ideation Wheel caused friction. Many participants felt it arrived too late to meaningfully shape their concepts. Teams reported enjoying the mix of high school and university collaboration during the first team-building activity, but interaction between the two participant groups declined significantly after the event. Once the structured activities ended, there was no continued interaction between the secondary school and university students, primarily due to the absence of opportunities for further engagement.

Research Methods

- Pre- and post-CGJ surveys (Microsoft Forms) on gaming experience, cultural perception, and European value awareness.
- Structured observation grid (space, facilitation, reflection, empowerment).
- Researcher field notes, vox pops, and game prototype analysis via mixed Likert and open-ended evaluations.

All participants provided informed consent, and data were anonymised through coded identifiers.

Documentation

Games were documented on the EPIC-WE Itch.io page with full descriptions, screenshots, and devlogs. Facilitators used to-do checklists and daily Discord updates to maintain submission consistency.

5.5.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 10 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Óbidos CGJ4](#)
- [The EPIC-WE Resource page for Óbidos CGJ4](#)

Two notable game prototypes included:

He Must Be Fed: Inspired by the myth of the Musaranhos, this game casts players as villagers serving a powerful deity to keep their community safe. Beneath its playful mechanics lies a commentary on obedience, oppression, and the cost of survival.

A Conquista (The Conquest): A stealth adventure inspired by the legend of the *Porta da Traição* (Door of Betrayal), where players infiltrate Moor-occupied Óbidos to open the town gates for liberation. The game links strategic play with historical themes of resistance and courage.

Table 23: Two example games from Óbidos CGJ4

Participant Feedback

Students described the CGJ as both inspiring and intense. The pre-CGJ folklore tour was widely appreciated for giving cultural depth and context, with one student commenting, “It was easier to design once we could picture the real places and stories.”

However, several participants mentioned that the Ideation Wheel felt out of place, since teams had already locked in their game ideas. Others suggested clearer facilitation and more structured checkpoints for feedback and integration between groups. Overall, participants found the experience valuable, citing teamwork, exposure to new design methods, and the cultural setting as highlights.

Many participants reflected that the CGJ pushed them beyond their comfort zones, requiring them to combine storytelling, mechanics, and heritage interpretation in ways they had never attempted before.

Figure 33, Secondary school students and university students interacting during Óbidos CGJ4.

Successes

- **Pre-CGJ activities** effectively prepared participants, allowing reflection and deeper cultural engagement before development began;
- **Team-building sessions** fostered collaboration across education levels, breaking down barriers and encouraging mixed-age teamwork;
- **Independent work by university students** led to focused, higher-quality prototypes that reflected stronger technical and conceptual maturity.

Challenges

- **Limited cross-group interaction** after the first day reduced the collaborative energy and exchange between high school and university participants;
- **Weak integration of European values** resulted from pre-formed ideas and late use of the Ideation Wheel;
- **Timing of facilitation tools** like the Ideation Wheel disrupted workflow, underscoring the need to introduce values-based design earlier in future editions.

5.6 Hilversum Cultural Hub CGJ4 (Fall 2025)

Figure 34, Participants creating collages for Hilversum CGJ4.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)

Date: September 10-16, 2025
Location: Dropstuff Media (DM) Shelter, Soesterberg, Netherlands; Utrecht University of Applied Sciences (HU), Utrecht, Netherlands; and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands
Duration: 4 days (spread over 2 weeks)
Participants: 28 students from Communication and Media Design (HU)
Number of Games: 7 prototypes
Theme: *Heritage Remixed* (Games through Culture), used archival materials to imagine the future relationship with water in the Netherlands

Table 24: Overview of Hilversum CGJ4

5.6.1 Introduction

Hilversum's fourth CGJ invited students to dive into the Netherlands' long and complicated relationship with water. Titled *Heritage Remixed: Tides of Heritage*, the CGJ asked participants to reinterpret archival materials, historical events, and cultural narratives about water, resilience, and community. Taking place across three very different creative sites, the CGJ mirrored its theme: movement, flow, and collaboration. Over four days, students explored how the Dutch battle against rising waters could become a story of shared values and translated into playful and meaningful experiences.

5.6.2 Partners / People Involved

- **Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV):** Hosted the final two days of the CGJ, providing cultural context, archive access, and exhibition space. Curatorial staff external to the project helped to select historical flood materials and co-create with AUAS a remix workshop enriching their understanding of water as heritage.
- **Dropstuff Media (DM):** Led creative facilitation, structured activities, and logistical coordination during the first two days, ensuring a consistent creative flow between sites.
- **Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS):** Led research before, during, and after the CGJ, and facilitated itch.io documentation; co-led the creation of cultural facilitation materials around water and heritage based on the research of one of the doctoral candidates in the cultural hub.
- **Utrecht University of Applied Sciences (HU):** Provided the core participant group from the Communication and Media Design programme, integrating the CGJ into coursework and assessment.
- **Youth Advisory Board (YAB):** Supported facilitation and reflection, helping to frame the theme in relation to youth perspectives on sustainability and climate resilience.
- **Expert Council and Jury:** Three expert lecturers in gaming from HU external to the project provided mid-way feedback for the expert council. The final jury included three independent game designers and experts in serious gaming.

5.6.3 Planning and Preparation

Preparation for the CGJ built on lessons from earlier glocal experiments. Planning meetings between NISV, Dropstuff, and HU focused on creating a “flowing” four-day structure that shifted from inspiration to creation across different sites. The Youth Advisory Board joined preparatory meetings to help adjust facilitation for mixed experience levels, particularly first-time gamemakers. A new collaboration model was introduced: each location had a specific creative purpose. Dropstuff's Shelter space provided a relaxed opening setting for

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storytelling and collective brainstorming; HU offered the structure and tools for design development; and NISV anchored the cultural exploration and public showcase.

Recruitment was streamlined through HU, embedding the CGJ directly within the Communication and Media Design (CMD) programme to ensure high engagement. This was admittedly to have two failed attempts earlier in the year to host this CGJ. In May 2025, a different technical college was meant to embed this CGJ in their course but stepped out at the last minute. The cultural hub pivoted to try open recruitment for July 2025 but failed to attract a sufficient number of participants to justify running the CGJ. DM helped to connect the cultural hub to the CMD programme at HU and its Immersive Experiences Minor, leading to a well-matched partnership for the kick-off of their Autumn semester.

To connect with the *Tides of Heritage* theme, facilitators from NISV and AUAS curated a focused selection of visual and audio materials from the NISV archive, including oral histories and footage of the 1953 North Sea flood. By assembling a small, curated package of the collection, they aimed to make the vast media archive more accessible and easier to navigate. This approach helped participants engage more readily with the materials, encouraging reflection and sparking new ideas.

Figure 35, Examples of the Future Sea Level Rise Scenarios for Hilversum CGJ4.

5.6.4 CGJ Execution

Connecting European Values, Cultural Heritage Sites, and Collections

The CGJ revolved around Dutch water heritage and how floods, resilience, and collective engineering have shaped national identity and culture. Students explored NISV's archives to uncover historical footage, photographs, and newsreels about the 1953 Watersnoodramp and earlier flood defences. These resources were shared through remixing workshops that explored Future Sea Level Rise Scenarios, inviting participants to reflect on trade-offs, justice, and identity in a future where water reshapes not only the land but also values, choices, and social contracts. In a playful exploration of European values such as cooperation, solidarity, and democracy under pressure, the Remix & Water workshop encouraged participants to design narrative collages for a game using archival stills. This process inspired teams to blend historical documentation with contemporary climate themes, showing how collective action and civic responsibility can be translated into mechanics of play. As one participant observed, “We don’t just live with water; it defines who we are.”

Schedule and Structure

The CGJ followed a four-day arc inspired by the E–P–I–C (Experience, Play, Imagine, Create) model, with each location representing a phase in the flow:

- **Day 1 (September 10, Dropstuff Media Shelter):** Experience Phase Kick-off, storytelling circle, “Flow Mapping” exercise linking personal memories of water to cultural stories, and group formation.
- **Day 2 (September 11, HU):** Introduction to design methods, ideation sprints, early paper prototyping, and a mini “Wave of Ideas” critique session with Expert Council.
- **Day 3 (September 15, NISV):** Archive exploration day including guided tours, short screenings of historical flood footage, and feedback sessions. Teams refined concepts using real archival materials.
- **Day 4 (September 16, NISV):** Final prototyping and showcase with Final Jury in the NISV foyer. Participants pitched to jury members, visitors, and project partners.

Participant Engagement

Participants showed strong ownership of their design direction. Working in small, interdisciplinary teams, they merged personal experiences of water with the historical and political dimensions of Dutch flood management. The dual focus of heritage and climate sparked meaningful discussions on sustainability, identity, and community responsibility.

Beginners benefited from structured facilitation tools like the Ideation Wheel and Wave of Ideas critique, while advanced students appreciated the freedom to explore more complex systems. Energy levels peaked during the museum days, where physical proximity to

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cultural artefacts provided new creative triggers. One participant reflected, “The archives made everything feel real. We were designing for the future, but learning from the past.”

Research Methods

- Pre- and post-CGJ surveys on game-making experience, European value understanding, and heritage perceptions.
- Vox pop interviews at NISV, supported by YAB members.
- Participatory observation and field notes by facilitators and researchers.
- Documentation through photos, videos, and pre-built itch.io devlogs pages

Documentation

Documentation was central to the process, supported by Dropstuff and NISV media teams. Each team maintained an itch.io page with at least two devlogs and final submissions. Photography and short interview videos captured the CGJ’s collaborative atmosphere and were later shared through EPIC-WE’s website and social media.

5.6.5 Outcomes

The Games

All 7 games from this CGJ can be found on:

- [The itch.io page for Hilversum CGJ4](#)

As of the submission of this deliverable, the specific [EPIC-WE resource page](#) for this CGJ was still under development.

Two notable game prototypes included:

<p>Smit and the Storm: A narrative escape room inspired by the 1953 North Sea flood. Players cooperate under time pressure to solve puzzles while a voice from the past, Smit, narrates his real experiences of survival. The game teaches teamwork and empathy, connecting human dignity and collective resilience with environmental awareness.</p>	<p>Meestromen: A fast-paced card game where players act as mayors managing water boards, balancing self-interest with collective survival. Using historical imagery from the archive, the game visualises sea-level rise and the politics of cooperation, challenging players to negotiate between democracy, risk, and solidarity.</p>
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Table 25: Two example games from Hilversum CGJ4

Participant Feedback

Participants described the CGJ as both exciting and demanding, with the fast-paced format pushing creativity under pressure. The climate-related themes resonated with the participants and they showed a genuine interest in connecting these to heritage materials. However, while the collection was presented as a resource for worldbuilding, participants primarily engaged with it on a visual level. For instance, one participant shared that “we saw a lot of still images containing animals, so we decided to do this and that” and another shared “we were captured by this guy on a boat and decided to create a character named Smith” as their reasoning for using specific cultural heritage materials. As a result, deeper exploration or critical reflection on the collection’s context and meaning was still a bit lacking for both participants and organisers in the final prototypes.

Feedback also indicated that the integration of EU values felt overly directive. Participants expressed that these values seemed externally imposed rather than meaningfully embedded in their design process. As one facilitator noted, “it wasn’t clear why we needed them as part of the game.” This perception suggested that while the civic dimension of the CGJ was strong in intention, the framing of values needed to feel more participant-driven and organically connected to the chosen themes. Despite these challenges, facilitators observed a marked increase in engagement compared to earlier editions, particularly when participants were encouraged to interpret the civic and environmental aspects of their games in their own way.

Figure 36, Participants celebrating their awards at the end of Hilversum CGJ4.

Successes

- **Strong thematic cultural heritage focus:** The water heritage theme provided emotional depth and immediate cultural relevance, inspiring authentic connections to Dutch identity and European values.
- **Collaborative flow across cultural hub locations:** The four-site structure created a literal and conceptual journey, sustaining engagement and mirroring the “movement” central to the CGJ.
- **Cultural heritage archive integration:** Teams used archival images, voices, and footage directly in their designs, showing measurable progress in cultural material application compared to earlier CGJs.

Challenges

- **Time compression:** The four-day schedule left limited room for iteration or deeper reflection, particularly for students new to cultural game design.
- **Balancing facilitation and autonomy:** Some groups desired clearer mid-CGJ checkpoints; others preferred self-direction, suggesting future CGJs could use flexible guidance tiers.
- **Technical documentation gaps:** Despite pre-set itch.io pages, not all teams completed full devlogs, indicating the need for dedicated documentation roles or incentives.

Reflections and Recommendations

06

6. Reflections and Recommendations

6.1 Reflections on Implementation of the CGJ Kit

The implementation of the innovated CGJ framework and CGJ Kit across the EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs has tested, expanded, and ultimately deepened the seven core principles introduced in the D3.2 Protocol 2 (Nørgård & Holflod, 2025, pp. 37–39). Across 12 CGJs, the framework’s ambition to turn game-making into a participatory and empowering cultural heritage method was repeatedly challenged by context, partnership dynamics, and youth realities. What follows reflects on how each principle was interpreted in practice, and how the iterative, glocal approach has transformed the CGJ framework from a structured protocol into a living, adaptive methodology.

Principle 1: Three Ways to Run Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams embrace a structured yet adjustable approach to game-making as culture-making, offering three levels of adaptability:

- *Fixed, where Cultural Game Jam elements are determined at the project or organisational level;*
- *Flexible, where the QH Cultural Hub tailor the process to local needs;*
- *Freeform, where youth shape their creative and collaborative journey based on the Cultural Game Jam Kit.*

These levels operate within a minimum viable model, balancing guidance and exploration. The Cultural Game Jam phases - Experience, Play, Imagine, Create - provide a straightforward yet open-ended process, allowing participants to engage with cultural themes and heritage by creating games through and for culture. Transition tools like the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council help participants transition from one phase to the next while refining ideas and integrating feedback and decisions.

Across the second round of CGJs, all three CGJ Kits (focused, flexible, and freeform) were tested. Hilversum’s *fixed* model during CGJ3 and CGJ4, where the CGJs were embedded in formal higher education minor programmes demonstrated the benefits of predictable structure and institutional alignment. It ensured continuity and participant commitment but also surfaced challenges around creative autonomy. Óbidos adopted a *flexible* model, blending structured research protocols with spontaneous cultural immersion in the historic town, allowing folklore and civic values to shape design. Aarhus represented the *freeform* mode: a slow jam stretched over multiple sessions that gave students agency to experiment with heritage remixing through AR/VR prototypes. This variation confirmed that the E–P–I–

C CGJ structure along with its methods and transition tools could adapt fluidly and offer scaffolding without constraining local imagination.

Principle 2: Aim for Cultural Participation, Co-Creation, and Empowerment

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as an act of cultural imagination and creation, where youth are not only receivers or consumers of heritage but active creators who shape its future. Participants engage in a co-creative process that positions game-making as a new form of culture-making through which youth create and showcase games through and for culture. These games directly engage cultural heritage, using it as an empowering medium for game-making. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership and belonging, allowing youth to engage with, reinterpret, and comment on cultural heritage in ways that reflect their own experiences and identities. By designing games that reflect their lived experiences, values, and collective imaginaries, participants develop a stronger sense of agency and belonging within cultural heritage and cultural environments.

Across all three cultural hubs, CGJs supported cultural participation by positioning youth as active co-creators in the cultural heritage discourse rather than passive consumers and recipients of cultural heritage.

To illustrate, in the Aarhus cultural hub, students in Digital Design and Computer Science reinterpreted Nordic artworks by transforming them into interactive cultural worlds that brought into question themes such as consumption and democracy. This demonstrated empowerment not only through cultural-creative reinterpretation but also through using heritage to express critical perspectives in their own empowered voice. In Óbidos cultural hub, the collaboration between secondary school pupils and university students created a peer-to-peer mentorship dynamic where younger participants felt confident proposing ideas and taking creative risks. Even though sustaining collaboration after the CGJ remained challenging, the event itself enabled young participants to step into roles as game designers and cultural storytellers. In Hilversum cultural hub, embedding CGJs within university minors supported longer-term empowerment by giving students recurring opportunities to continue developing their games through/for culture concepts beyond the CGJ event.

Across all cultural hubs, empowerment was strongest when participants had the freedom to choose their themes, interpret heritage materials, and guide their own design direction. Through this co-creative environment, CGJs enabled youth to use cultural heritage as a medium for expressing identity, exploring values, and imagining cultural futures on their

own terms, with the three examples above representing only a small selection of the many forms of empowered participation demonstrated across the twelve CGJs.

Principle 3: Foster Cultural Curiosity and Creativity

Cultural Game Jams cultivate an environment where curiosity and creativity drive cultural exploration, encouraging youth to become culture-makers through cultural storytelling and game design. The game-making process fosters deep engagement with past, present, and future cultural narratives by allowing participants to experiment, remix, and reimagine cultural heritage through the creation of games through and for culture. Through Cultural Game Jams, culture becomes not a static artefact of the past but an evolving and participatory practice that youth actively shape by creating cultural experiences, interactions, and expressions.

Curiosity emerged as the engine of engagement, especially when cultural material was tangible and sensory.

This proved particularly visible in the fourth iteration of CGJs during the *Heritage Remixed* CGJs. In the Hilversum cultural hub, cultural heritage curiosity was sparked during their fourth CGJ through the Remix & Water workshop and depot tours, translating abstract concepts like our future relationship with water into concrete cultural encounters. Aarhus cultural hub used embodied exercises such as “Step into the painting” to activate sensory cultural heritage curiosity, prompting playful and philosophical responses to the cultural heritage collections. Óbidos cultural hub used guided culture walks and myth-based activities encouraged cultural-creative interpretation, even when the cultural connections were uneven. The CGJs confirmed that cultural heritage curiosity grows when participants encounter culture experientially rather than didactically and when creative constraints (like using public-domain art or folklore fragments) invite imaginative risk-taking rather than rote reuse.

Principle 4: Cultivate an “Epic We”

Cultural Game Jams are designed to cultivate a sense of community and collective creativity that transcends the individual and fosters an experience of becoming part of an “epic we” in cultural heritage. This approach requires creating conditions that encourage collaboration, relational engagement, and shared cultural exploration, where differences interact productively rather than competitively. By embracing tensions and dissimilarities as opportunities for cultural curiosity and co-creation, Cultural Game Jams become more

than game-making events. They serve as transformative cultural environments that nurture engaged participation, cultural empowerment, and collective culture-making.

The notion of the *epic we*, or collective creativity beyond individual contribution, manifested in the co-creative rhythms of the CGJs.

Moments of togetherness often defined the most memorable experiences: the public EXPO in Aarhus, where 18 teams showcased XR games side by side; the team-building exercises in Óbidos that bridged age and disciplinary divides; the peer playtests in Hilversum where participants took hours to try out each other's games and would have taken more time if the building was not about to close. These events demonstrated how collaboration became cultural in itself so that participants learned to negotiate differences, translate expertise, and co-author meaning. Yet sustaining this collective spirit required deliberate facilitation and attention to rhythm; where sessions became overly lecture-like or fragmented, the sense of "we" risked dissolving.

Principle 5: Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making

At the heart of Cultural Game Jams is a commitment to value-sensitive cultural design, where cultural, ethical, and societal considerations shape the game-making process. Participants are encouraged to critically examine themes such as citizenship, European identity, and the evolving and participatory nature of cultural heritage, and to engage with these themes through co-creation and the development of games through and for culture. Participants explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions, narratives, and aesthetics. This fosters a deeper awareness of how games through and for culture can function as methods for cultural critique, reflection, expression, and empowerment.

Value sensitivity proved one of the most intellectually demanding yet rewarding aspects of the CGJ framework.

Across cultural hubs, participants grappled with how to embed fairness, freedom, or democracy not just as topics but as gameplay *mechanics*. For example, In Hilversum cultural hub's *Viral Spiral*, press freedom and misinformation were materialised through gameplay choices about sharing or censoring news. In Óbido cultural hub's *A Conquista*, human dignity and freedom were woven into a retelling of the town's legendary "Door of

Betrayal.” Aarhus cultural hub’s *Roomination* and *ReStory* explored existential questions of cultural agency and belonging through immersive art interpretation. These examples reveal how reflective design prompts that were supported by CGJ methods and tools like the Ideation Wheel helped translate abstract values into interactive form, though facilitators noted that participants often needed more time and guidance to deepen cultural engagement beyond surface symbolism.

Principle 6: Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation

Cultural Game Jams challenge audience-oriented notions of cultural heritage by engaging game-making as a powerful method for action-oriented cultural engagement. Rather than approaching heritage as something to be preserved or consumed, Cultural Game Jams invite participants to reimagine, remix, remediate, and recreate cultural works and narratives in their games through and for culture. This approach highlights the potential of games as interactive systems and experiences capable of provoking thought, sparking dialogue, and engaging audiences as players within cultural heritage. By embedding cultural inquiry, interpretation, and innovation into the game-making process, Cultural Game Jams contribute to a broader recognition of the potential of games as culture.

CGJs positioned game-making not as a derivative exercise but as a form of cultural innovation and interpretation. Cultural heritage interpretation occurred when participants analysed and reframed cultural materials to express new meanings, while cultural heritage innovation emerged as they transformed those materials into entirely new cultural experiences through play. The Aarhus cultural hub slow jam exemplified this dual process: students remixed public-domain artworks into XR environments, shifting static images into participatory cultural encounters that invited new readings of the collection. In Hilversum cultural hub, games from the *Tides of Heritage* CGJ reframed historical flood narratives as civic simulations about climate resilience, demonstrating how heritage can be used to imagine alternative futures. Óbidos cultural hub’s folklore-based games employed humour and satire to reinterpret myths for contemporary audiences, updating traditional narratives while keeping their cultural resonance intact. Together, these examples show how CGJs encouraged active reinterpretation and creative transformation, allowing cultural heritage institutions to operate not only as custodians of the past but as facilitators of cultural futures.

Principle 7: Create games through and for culture and cultural transformation

Cultural Game Jams position game-making as both a reflection on and an active engagement with culture, resulting in the creation of games through and for culture. By embedding historical, imaginative, and societal themes into games, and by inviting game-makers to engage with heritage through cultural transformation, Cultural Game Jams generate games that serve as immersive forms of cultural storytelling. This dual focus on games through culture (exploring and incorporating cultural heritage as game-making material toward new interactive cultural expressions) and games for culture (imagining and enacting values, identities, and collective responsibility in culture and society) ensures that Cultural Game Jams and their resulting games extend beyond the transmission of cultural heritage.

The deliberate alternation between games for culture and games through culture across the third and fourth CGJs successfully tested these two applications of the CGJ framework and Kit but also exposed a consistent tension between them.

Rather than representing a strict conceptual divide, the two modes functioned more as scales along a spectrum, with CGJs leaning differently depending on the cultural heritage theme, materials, and facilitation approach. For example, participants in the *That's Not Fair!* CGJs that followed the Games for Culture CGJ Kit produced strong explorations of fairness, freedom, and dignity, yet some groups struggled to connect these societal themes to specific forms of heritage, whether tangible, intangible, or natural. Conversely, the games developed in the *Heritage Remixed* CGJs that followed the Games through Culture CGJ Kit grounded their designs firmly in cultural heritage artifacts and local histories, but at times incorporated European values more unevenly or implicitly.

The pattern was not uniform across cultural hubs. Óbidos cultural hub offered a clear example of how the two modes can reinforce one another. In the game *Blue Brigade*, censorship was expressed directly through gameplay while drawing from Óbidos' identity as a City of Literature, showing that democratic values can be meaningfully integrated when the theme and heritage source align well. These insights suggest that some forms of heritage or some CGJ themes naturally lend themselves more readily to value integration, while others require more intentional scaffolding from facilitators. Taken together, the experiences across cultural hubs indicate that games for culture and games through culture offer distinct but complementary pathways for meaningful cultural engagement. Achieving a more organic synthesis between civic reflection and heritage engagement remains an important next step for further refining the CGJ Kit.

6.2 Reflections from the Youth Advisory Boards

The **Youth Advisory Board (YAB)** members from Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos described their involvement as simultaneously exciting and eye-opening, providing the cultural hubs a unique window into how youth participation can shape cultural co-creation. Many reflected positively on the chance to move from participants to contributors by joining planning meetings, assisting in facilitation, and observing the process firsthand. They appreciated opportunities to voice ideas and see them integrated into CGJ structures, such as museum tours, feedback sessions, and exhibition planning. Pitching to experts, taking part in juries, and contributing to the preparation of later CGJs helped several YAB members gain confidence in public speaking, teamwork, and event organisation. As one member wrote, *“I would call it a success that I had the opportunity to share my thoughts during the preparation of the CGJ, that the whole team was happy to hear my comments and ideas.”*

At the same time, YAB members were candid about the challenges they faced. Some found their responsibilities unclear at the outset and struggled to understand how their input influenced final decisions both locally and for the overall EPIC-WE project. Language barriers occasionally made observation difficult, and group dynamics could be intimidating, especially for those who joined alone or found themselves in socially homogeneous teams. One YAB participant reflected that, *“It was hard being the only stranger in a group of friends and the only queer person in a group of straight men.”* Others noted that while the YAB structure was empowering in principle, at times they felt distant from the core coordination work and wanted more transparency about planning decisions. Across cultural hubs, a recurring suggestion was to establish clearer safety protocols and communication channels to help participants feel comfortable and supported.

Another central reflection concerned fair remuneration, time balance, and sustainability. Although some YAB and youth members were compensated through stipends or research assistantships, their participation in the CGJs was often a secondary activity alongside jobs or study. As a result, their availability varied from CGJ to CGJ, and a few early YAB members had to step back as they struggled to balance these responsibilities with professional and personal commitments. This created tension between the aim of consistent, equitable, and meaningful youth participation and the reality of fluctuating time and capacity. The model worked best when YAB members could participate consistently across multiple CGJs, as they grew more comfortable with the inherent ambiguity and evolving structure that cultural hub teams were navigating. Looking ahead, YAB members recommended clearer role definitions, regular check-ins, fair compensation for co-facilitation, and stronger continuity between events to sustain engagement. As one participant summarised, *“Being treated as an equal collaborator also means being valued like one.”* Despite these challenges, YAB members consistently expressed pride in their

contributions and appreciation for the trust placed in them and seeing their involvement not just as advisory, but as a meaningful step toward shared leadership and equitable collaboration in cultural innovation.

6.3 Key Takeaways and Hindsight Reflections

The following synthesis is organised by sector to help future organisers understand the specific roles, challenges, and strengths each actor brings to the CGJ process. This structure reflects the “quadruple helix” model at the heart of EPIC-WE, where collaboration across heritage, creative practice, education, and youth participation forms the foundation of co-creation. By distilling sector-specific takeaways and hindsight reflections from four rounds of CGJs across Europe, this section aims to provide practical insight for organisations wishing to adopt or adapt the framework in their own local or glocal contexts.

6.3.1 Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI)

Key Takeaways: The participating CHI, ARoS, Municipality of Óbidos, and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision, discovered that CGJs are a powerful way to activate cultural heritage collections and engage new audiences in creative interpretation. Whether in the galleries of ARoS, deep in the archive depot of NISV, or walking the medieval streets of Óbidos, the participating CHIs professionals found that engaging heritage through game-making and making heritage “playable” unlocked unexpected forms of participation. By positioning cultural heritage artefacts, landscapes and narratives as creative material for game-making, CHIs helped participants see heritage as living, engaging, and dynamic. The events also introduced audience engagement innovations such as public playtesting, youth-led showcases, and interactive EXPOs, which invited visitors to co-experience prototypes instead of simply viewing them. These strategies revealed how youth participants’ curious, irreverent, and experimental approaches could bring fresh relevance to archival and museum content as well as cultural landscapes by reframing them in terms of societal challenges, cultural identity, and cultural values.

Hindsight: In practice, CHIs learned that balancing institutional priorities with the open, improvisational nature of CGJs required careful preparation. Many heritage professionals underestimated the time needed to curate accessible, rights-cleared materials that could be meaningfully integrated into cultural heritage games. Limited familiarity with game-making sometimes led to overambitious expectations about what could be achieved in short timeframes. Earlier collaboration with facilitators and educators would have helped translate curatorial concepts into usable creative cultural heritage prompts. A key insight was that heritage needs mediation. Short lists of selected materials, simple thematic

framing, and examples of earlier “heritage-based” games (e.g. games through culture and games for culture from earlier CGJs) can make the cultural-creative process more intuitive for participants.

6.3.2 Creative Industry Partners (CI)

Key Takeaways: The creative industry partners, Filmby Aarhus, Battlesheep, and Dropstuff Media, found that CGJs thrive on friction and that differences in working styles and expectations between sectors sparked innovation rather than blocking it. They also discovered that youth participants were often more capable, motivated, and imaginative than expected. For creative professionals used to structured production pipelines, facilitating in an educational and cultural heritage context required flexibility and humility. The co-creation QH Cultural Hub model where artists, teachers, and curators all share ownership proved to be an effective way to blend professional practice with cultural heritage experimentation.

Hindsight: The creative partners reflected that recruitment, planning, and alignment across institutions were far more time-consuming than typical commercial projects. Misaligned expectations, especially regarding time, intellectual property, and decision-making occasionally caused tension. The partners also recognised that introducing too many creative tools or design frameworks early in the CGJ could overwhelm participants pointing towards a Fixed or Focused CGJ Kit. Iterating and simplifying CGJ Kit methods over time produced better outcomes. Finally, clearer agreements on logistics, responsibilities, and communication across sectors would have improved efficiency and reduced the burden on facilitators.

6.2.3 Higher Education Institutions (HEI)

Key Takeaways: The participating Higher education institutions, Aarhus University, Lusófona University, and the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences found that CGJs created unique opportunities for experiential, social, and embodied-material cultural heritage learning that connected theory and practice through engaging cultural heritage through game-making. CGJs and the CGJ Kit encouraged interdisciplinary collaboration among students from art, design, and media studies, and functioned as laboratories for reflective cultural heritage participation and creation. Embedding research directly within design, through methods like observation and devlogs, proved to be an effective way to study co-creation without disrupting it. HEIs also observed that participants gained a stronger understanding of cultural heritage sites, collections, and values as well as their

own cultural identity and belonging when those topics were grounded in tangible, local cultural heritage contexts.

Hindsight: HEIs learned that motivation and skill diversity among students required adaptive facilitation. Recruitment and scheduling across academic calendars posed significant logistical challenges. The participating universities at times underestimated the workload of coordinating with external partners while managing research obligations. Moreover, balancing the roles of teacher, researcher, and facilitator created tension for the HEI professionals participating in each cultural hub. Clearer guidance on evaluation criteria and earlier integration of research protocols would have reduced confusion and improved consistency across cultural hubs. Finally, educators found that too much abstraction, especially around values, risked alienating younger participants unless the concepts were linked to personal experience and concrete cultural heritage material.

6.3.4 Youth Advisory Boards (YAB)

Key Takeaways: Across cultural hubs, YAB members demonstrated that youth participation is most effective when it is active, visible, and continuous. They valued being treated as collaborators rather than token representatives, describing their experience as empowering, modern, and socially meaningful. By contributing to planning, facilitation, and evaluation, they gained practical skills and a stronger sense of agency. When given defined roles such as co-facilitators, observers, or jurors, YAB members felt their perspectives genuinely shaped outcomes. Consistent communication and recognition of their contributions were crucial to maintaining motivation and commitment over time.

Hindsight: YAB members also recognised recurring structural challenges that limited continuity and inclusivity. Early uncertainty about roles and decision-making blurred the boundaries between “advisor” and “participant.” Competing academic and professional commitments, coupled with partial remuneration, sometimes led to uneven engagement and, in a few cases, notable fatigue and needing to stop their participation. Language differences and social imbalances within groups affected comfort and collaboration. Looking back, YAB members stressed the importance of clear onboarding, transparent communication, and explicit inclusion tools to safeguard wellbeing and equity. Sustained participation across multiple CGJs deepened youth ownership and confidence, but achieving this required predictable compensation, ongoing mentorship, and an explicit invitation to shape instead of just support the process.

6.4 Recommendations for Future Cultural Game Jams

1. **Start simple, then iterate and expand.** Begin with a clear and limited selection of CGJ Kit methods and tools, then iterate and expand from there based on the ambition, experience, skills, and working styles of the incoming participants and facilitators. Experienced game-makers may build on their own creative processes and use the cultural heritage parts of the CGJ Kit, while others benefit from more structured approaches in both game-making and culture-making. Knowing your participants experience within games and cultural heritage to tailor the CGJ Kit accordingly ensures it supports cultural creativity.
2. **Pre-curate cultural heritage resources.** CHIs should prepare a dedicated, rights-cleared selection of accessible cultural heritage resources such as artworks, images, audio, texts, and other tangible heritage resources that connect directly to the CGJ theme. Starting with a focused, well-framed set of resources reduces complexity for participants and supports deeper cultural engagement.
3. **Integrate European values through lived experience.** Connect abstract values like fairness, democracy, or dignity to relatable cultural heritage collections, stories, local sites, themes, or personal contexts.
4. **Embed research in the creative CGJ flow.** Use devlogs, observation, and reflection as part of the CGJ process to capture participants work and reflections. As a researcher be careful to not disrupt the flow of game-making in counterproductive ways. Make clear for participants that researchers take part in the CGJ.
5. **Establish cross-sector cultural hub collaboration from the outset.** Establish clear communication channels, shared calendars and collaborative “meetings in the middle” on a regular basis among CHI, CI, HEI, and Youth partners in the cultural hub from the outset to align practices, logistics, and expectations.
6. **Build in pre-jam and post-jam activities.** Use pre-jam activities to introduce the CGJ framework and CGJ Kit, discuss and engage cultural heritage collections, sites, and values, and facilitate team building before game-making begins. Post-jam activities could include inviting YCs to support and co-develop future CGJs with CHIs or the further development of the resulting games through/for culture with CIs.
7. **Support YAB continuity and compensation.** When youth partners are involved in planning and running CGJs, long-term engagement is usually more rewarding and empowering than short-term participation. To sustain this continuity, it is important to highlight the value, benefits, or offer fair compensation. To create impact devise clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and regular check-ins. These practices help prevent disengagement fatigue and create a healthy, ongoing rhythm of collaboration throughout both the planning, execution, and evaluation phases.

8. **Implement safety, inclusion, and diversity protocols.** Provide explicit protocols and guidance on respectful collaboration, value-sensitive discussion, inclusivity, diversity, and channels for reporting discomfort.
9. **Keep CGJ Kits modular and accessible.** Use the CGJ Kit to create a strong focus on cultural heritage and culture-making in the game-making process. Adopt and adapt the CGJ Kit to simplify language, visualise process steps, and deliver adaptable processes and methods that can be tailored to different cultural heritage themes and contexts. The CGJ Kit should be adapted to work for both short CGJ sessions, multi-day CGJs, or even “slow jams” spanning several weeks, and for youth with varying levels of experience in game-making and culture-making to participate in empowering ways.
10. **Foster glocal collaboration and connections.** Link up with other cultural hubs or cross-sector partners from outside your local site to organize and run parallel or theme-linked CGJs to enhance cultural heritage and values’ exchange, shared learnings, inspiring cross-hub interchange of games through/for culture, and comparative cultural-creative productions and reflections.

Conclusion

07

7. Conclusion

Across the QH Cultural Hubs of Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos, the Cultural Game Jams and associated CGJ Kit demonstrated how **game-making can act as a bridge between cultural heritage and youth participation**, transforming museums, archives, historical cities, and universities into sites of collective cultural heritage imagination, engagement, and inquiry. Through the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub model and CGJ framework and CGJ Kit, YCs engaged not only with tangible cultural heritage artefacts and intangible cultural heritage values and histories, but also with the living values and civic perspectives they embody. Each cultural heritage site adopted and adapted the CGJ Kit and framework to its own local rhythms and contexts. Together, these **12 CGJ interventions** engaged **424 young participants** and supported the creation of **108 games through/for culture prototypes** that revealed how heritage can be engaged and reimaged as a cultural material for empowerment, reflection, belonging, and citizenship. They also demonstrated that the process of cultural heritage co-creation is itself an empowering and imaginative form of cultural participation.

The EPIC-WE project's cumulative findings reaffirm that game-making as a form of culture-making is not only a method of learning about heritage and values, but a practice of engaging, transforming, and expressing them. The Cultural Game Jam Kit and framework, with its adaptable E-P-I-C phases, methods, and transition tools, proved strong and supportive enough to provide scaffolded guidance for first-time game-makers while also offering sufficient openness for experienced game-makers to bring in their own creative processes, experiment with cultural heritage, and push the framework in new directions – while ensuring a focus on cultural heritage and culture-making.

Key lessons emerged around balancing cultural creativity with CGJ facilitation, embedding research in design, and sustaining equitable and empowering youth participation through including them as partners and co-creators in the form of YABs. As the QH Cultural Hubs evolved and cross-sector partnerships and collaboration deepened over time, they revealed how cultural heritage game-making can surface ethical tensions, empower diverse voices, and cultivate shared ownership of our cultural heritage and values. The insights from running 12 local and glocal CGJ interventions and later analysing the data collected from these CGJs point towards next steps in further refining the CGJ Kit and framework as an empowering participatory format for engaging and co-creating cultural heritage and cultural innovation.

Future QH Cultural Hubs can use the CGJ Kit and framework innovated and developed in the project to deepen cross-sector collaboration, empower youth in game-making and

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culture-making, and continue evolving the practice of making culture playable through Cultural Game Jams and the creation of games through culture and games for culture.

References and Appendix

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Appendix

Case Study Template

The event analysis is a descriptive analysis of the game jam. It should describe how the cultural game jam was run by explaining the organizational process, the execution and the lessons learned for the next game jam.

As described in the EPIC-WE Research Flow, the goal is to write a 10-page analysis for each game jam, preferably accompanied by illustrations.

Template

1. Introduction

- **Overview of the CGJ:** Provide a summary of the game jam, date, location
- **Theme:** Describe the main theme of the game jam

2. Background

- **Iteration (if applicable):** Describe the main changes to the game jam structure compared to the previous game jam's lessons learned
- **Partners / People involved:** Describe the organizations and people (CI/CHI/HEI/Youth) involved in the GJ and their roles. This also includes people from outside of the project, such as security or floor managers

3. Planning and Preparation

- **Planning Process:** Outline the steps taken to plan the CGJ. How did the different partners (CHI, CI, HEI, Youth) work together and what were their roles? Were specific methods used in the planning process to facilitate collaboration (i.e. design sprints)? How were Youth involved in the planning process? In terms of the execution of these roles, what worked well, what didn't work well, and how could it be improved?
- **Toolkit:** How was the CGJ toolkit (phases, methods, values, transition tools, youth roles, etc.) integrated, adapted, or not used? What was the feedback and experience from the different partners (CHI, CI, HEI, Youth) in the planning phase of the game jam? What tools and materials worked well, which didn't work so well and how could use/integration of materials be improved?

- **Recruitment:** Discuss the strategies used to recruit participants. What worked well, what didn't work well, how could it be improved?
- **Values & Cultural Collection:** How were the EU values and Cultural collection planned to be integrated into the game jam design process? What worked well, what didn't work well and how could it be improved?
- **Logistics:** Explain how the logistics were managed, such as setting up at the CHI, setting up online platforms (e.g. itch, discord), and arranging for necessary equipment and resources.

4. CGJ Execution

- **Production Documents:** Please include links to all relevant planning/production documents (e.g. production plans, event timeline, participant communications, materials shared with participants, etc that help illustrate your game jam execution process.
- **Schedule and Structure:** Provide a detailed schedule of the CGJ. Explain how the game jam was structured (for example in different phases). Please reflect on the flow/timing of the event and its activities regarding worked well, what didn't work well and how it could be improved.
- **Location:** Describe the location(s) and their setting used throughout the game jam.
- **Participant Engagement:** Describe how participants were engaged throughout the CGJ, including any icebreakers, team formation activities, and design methods. What was the agency of the participants in decision-making? For example, in selecting themes, EU values or design methods (RQ3).
- **Support:** Detail the support systems in place for participants, such as mentorship from industry experts and resources provided.
- **Facilitation:** How did the CHI/CI organize the facilitation of the game jam together (RQ2.1)? How were the roles divided? What worked well in terms of facilitation (mentoring, introduction to activities, and guidance etc), what did not work so well, and how could it be improved?
- **Documentation of CGJ:** Please describe the documentation methods used to capture the overall game jam for communication, publicity and project history. What worked well, what did not work well, and what could be improved?
- **Documentation of Games:** Please describe the documentation methods used to document the games for research and communications purposes. What worked well, what did not work well, and what could be improved?
- **Research:** Describe the research methods used to collect data before, during and after the game jam. This can include methods such as surveys, voxpops and

observations. Explain how they were carried out and what went well or could be improved.

5. Outcomes

- **Awards and pitch criteria:** Mention any awards given and criteria for selection.
- **Participant Feedback:** Summarize feedback received from participants regarding their experience, challenges faced, and suggestions for improvement (RQ3).
- **Successes & Challenges:** Identify what went well during the CGJ or could be improved. Think about topics such as recruitment, collaboration between partners, the integration of cultural heritage and EU values in the games produced and the embedding of cultural artefacts & EU values. For the challenges, describe how they were addressed or could be mitigated in the future.

7. Lessons Learned

- **Key Takeaways:** Highlight the main lessons learned from each project partner (CHI, CI, HEI, Youth) from organizing, running the CGJ and using the available toolkits.
- **Hindsight Knowledge:** What are some things that would have been helpful to know in advance of the game jam?
- **Recommendations for Future CGJ:** Provide actionable recommendations for future game jams based on the insights gained.

Local Thematic Analysis Template

Preface:

The local thematic analysis qualitatively examines all available and produced data through deductive and inductive processes. The deductive process draws from a codebook developed primarily from the project research questions, with strong affinities towards Protocol 3, the project Core Concepts, and the EPIC-WE Proposal Part B, which will also be integrated into the discussion. The inductive approach is a flexible way to develop codes that might not be part of the codebook but would still be relevant for analysis. If a code is, e.g., empowerment, inductive codes might be societal, social, identity, cultural, collaborative, individual, challenging, disempowering, conflictual, power relations, etc., or associated words like influence, motivation, and engagement, that could all be connected to the deductive code of empowerment. From the codes – and overlying categories, discussed in this document as clustered codes – and research across data, themes are produced, which are the foci of analysis.

The thematic analysis includes various data sources (e.g., interviews, observations, visual and auditory material, questionnaires, games, game concepts, etc.) to examine cultural game jams, the enactment of the quadruple helix system and cultural hubs, and the relevant situations, contexts, materials, spaces, processes, etc. If needed, thematic analysis using a reflexive approach is described last in the document.

As displayed in the EPIC-WE Research Flow, the goal is to write at least ten pages in narrative form, preferably accompanied by illustrations.

Template

1. Introduction

What data is the analysis based on, and how was the analysis undertaken - reflexively considering how the researchers approached data analysis through 'reflexive thematic analysis'.

The analysis is based on various sources of data from the x game jam by the Y hub. The table below provides an overview of the data.

How & What	Content
Data collection & Analysis	
Context	
Participants and recruitment	
Programme	
Methods and materials	
When & where	

X nr of researchers undertook thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019) using deductive and inductive coding across all the data. The table below provides an overview of the coding process, going from 1) theory-driven codes to 2) data-driven codes, 3) clustering the codes, and 4) developing themes from them.

Overview of themes:

Deductive/Theory-driven code	Inductive/Data driven codes	Clustered codes	Theme

Deductive/Theory-driven code	Inductive/Data driven codes	Clustered codes	Theme

2. **Theme Analysis 1**
 - a. Detailed analysis of each theme and contextualisation
3. **Theme Analysis 2**
 - a. Detailed analysis of each theme and contextualisation
4. **Theme Analysis 3**
 - a. Detailed analysis of each theme and contextualisation
5. **Theme Analysis 4**
 - a. Detailed analysis of each theme and contextualisation
6. **Discussion**
 - a. Connections between these analyses and RQs: Do the analyses of themes answer or provide partial answers to the RQs, and in which ways?
 - b. Discussion of themes analyses concerning methodology: e.g., strengths, weaknesses, applications, implications, contingencies, and biases related to DBR/EDR/design interventions.

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- c. Connections to EPIC-WE Outcomes and Wider Impacts: How do the results and findings from the thematic analysis relate to and influence the outcomes and wider impact goals of EPIC-WE?
 - d. Write a brief methodological reflection considering how the researchers approached data analysis through, e.g., semantic/descriptive and latent/prescriptive analysis, deductive/inductive, and in creating themes/patterns.

7. Conclusion

8. References

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2019). Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis, *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 11:4, 589–597. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806>

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Local Games Analysis Template

EPIC-WE Game Jam

1. EPIC-WE Game Jam description (max 350 characters, fill out by EPIC-WE team):

Example: Lusófona University CGJ1, February 2024, in Óbidos. The team consisted of António Rodrigues – Programmer and Game Designer, Gabriela Branco, UI and 2D Art.

Internal Procedure

Each HUB must start by giving information about the EPIC-WE and the goal of the analysis to the participants. Each HUB must ensure that participants have all the necessary materials to conduct the game analysis. This includes providing one computer per participant, with the required games pre-installed and tested for functionality. Each computer should contain only a combination of two games, and this combination should be unique. For instance (game1, game2) is the same as (game 2, game 1) and a specific game should be on two computers. A list with the 2 games per computer is calculated before installation. Researchers should verify previously if the installation is correct. This list, to be printed, has also a space for the participant ID.

For each participant, a code (i.e. GA01) must be given to ensure confidentiality (the participant ID) and for each survey, the same code must be entered by the researcher. The name of the game must be selected by the researcher in the game analysis instrument. A QR code with the game analysis instrument should be available (i.e: project it in the room) for participants, after they filled the Informed consent.

Instructions for participants

Participants should be welcomed, and informed they will analyse games prototypes created during an EPIC-WE game jam about the cultural theme X and European Value(s) Y.

They should consult the game dev logs available in the document available in each computer (it is a document on desktop with the game name that contains a link to the respective game itch.io). They should do the analysis in the instrument that is accessed by the QR code. After they finish the 1st games analyse, they should inform the researchers to start the second analysis. They could have a break if they need to during the process, and to leave the analysis at any moment, and to do so they should inform the researchers. If there are no questions from the participants, the analysis can proceed.

1. The informed consent available in the PC must be filled at first by the participant;
2. To access the GA analysis instrument, they should scan the QR code;
3. The game analysis starts;
4. The participants must play the game until they feel they know the game.

Doing the Analysis

2.1 Researcher background description (max 250 characters):

2.1.1 Describe your prior game experience in games, selecting the answers that apply. (multiple choice)

As a player

As a game designer

As a game developer

As a game artist

As a User Experience/User Interface (UX/UI)

Other: (open question max 200 characters)

2.1.2 How often do you have contact with games (including playing games, creating or producing them)?

- Very frequently (daily).
- Frequently (a few times a week)
- Occasionally (few times a month)
- Rarely (once in a couple of months)
- Very Rarely (couple time a year or less)
- Never have contact

2.2 Date and place:

Indicate the date (range) when and region where the game analysis was conducted.

3. Game Prototype Analysis

3.1 What is the name of the game?

(multiple choice question, where each HUB puts the list of games)

3.2 Full data from itch.io:

3.2.2 The developer's description:

(EXAMPLE – Copy from itch.io)

3.3 Software version:

Indicate the specific software version of the analysed game if applied (example: Game Engine).

3.4 Platform:

Indicate the platform(s) the game(s) was played on.

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3.5 Genre:

What describes the genre of the game.

Insert Tags: (examples: 1st person shooter, RPG, tower-defence, 2D platform, 3D platform, moba, real-time strategy, simulation, hidden objects...)

3.6 Type:

What describes this game type better?

Insert Tags: (examples: single player, co-op, multiplayer, split screen, local co-op, headphones needed)

On a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "Strongly Disagree" and 7 "Strongly Agree", please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Somewhat Disagree	4. Neither Agree or Disagree	5. Somewhat Agree	6. Agree	7. Strongly Agree
The topic is well incorporated into the game.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I found it interesting to learn about the topic through the game.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I liked the visuals of the game.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I liked the storytelling of the game.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The game mechanics are entertaining.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The game is original/innovative.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I liked the game and I would play a more complete version of it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Researcher reflections

4.1 Please describe the game in your own words (max 500 characters):

4.2 Are there any learning outcomes?

Yes or No answer

4.2.1 If yes, what are they? (max 500 characters):

4.3 Are they linked to the cultural theme? Please be specific (max 250 characters):

4.4 What values does the game express, if any? (max 500 characters):

4.5 Does the game convey social issues? Please elaborate. (max 500 characters):

4.6 How do you see it as a game for and through culture? (max 500 characters)

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

**Funded by
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